

Discussion paper on mechanisms that can ensure that EU policies are coherent with SDGs

MATS Deliverable 4.2

MATS

making agricultural trade sustainable

Funded by
the European Union

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101000751.

Summary

This discussion paper examines the degree of policy coherence between the EU's internal and external policies shaping agricultural trade and the alignment of EU agricultural trade policy and trade agreements in economic, social and environmental terms. Our analysis of all the agreements and political initiatives that make up the 'core' trade policy of the EU shows that a small number of trade agreements take into consideration in their provisions the environmental impact of agriculture, including issues such as the impact on soil and water quality, soil erosion and pollution by agricultural chemicals, the management of impacts through the use of antibiotics and decontaminants, conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity, and genetically modified organisms.

Three policy issues are examined from the multiplicity of policies enacted or initiated by the EU: organic farming certification, food safety regulations, and Green Deal and Biodiversity strategy targets. Three of the 15 MATS case studies (CS) have been selected to receive feedback on the region- or sector-specific impacts of the policies examined. A questionnaire was prepared and sent to project partners of the three CSs to get some feedback on the role the specific policy is playing in the CS and the sectors concerned. The first task of this exercise was to evaluate the specific policies within the framework of the specific CSs as far as their contribution to achieving the relevant Goals and Targets of the Sustainable Development Agenda 2030 were concerned. The Task leaders prepared a list of Goals and Targets and sent it to the CS partners for this purpose. Partners were asked to evaluate the policy according to the criteria provided by the International Council for Science (2017). Further, more policy-specific questions were posed to elicit the CS-relevant information necessary to analyse the results. Finally, policy proposals were provided by CS partners.

The conclusions of the analysis are divided into two parts: first, policy coherence and sustainability issues in EU trade-related policies, and second, policy proposals to increase coherence with sustainable trade; these policy proposals concern the EU organic farming certification scheme, the harmonised food safety regulations for EU imports, and agricultural extension and training.

Deliverable title: Discussion paper on mechanisms that can ensure that EU policies are coherent with SDGs

Deliverable number: D4.2

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Due date: 31 December 2023

Submission date: 29 December 2023

Nature¹: Other

Dissemination Level²: Public

Work Package: WP4

Lead Beneficiary: Agricultural University of Athens (AUA)

Contributing Beneficiaries: University of Helsinki (UH), Economic and Social Research Foundation (ESRF), Oxfam Solidarite (OXFAM)

¹ R = Report, P = Prototype, D = Demonstrator, O = Other

² PU = Public, CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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List of Abbreviations

AA	Association Agreement
ACP	African, Caribbean, and Pacific
AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
AoA	Agreement on Agriculture
AROS	Asia Regional Organic Standard
ARS	African Regional Standard
ASEAN	Association of Southeast Asian Nations
ASOA	ASEAN Standard for Organic Agriculture
BDS	Biodiversity Strategy
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CAPRI	Common Agricultural Policy Regionalised Impact
CETA	Comprehensive and Economic Trade Agreement
CGE	Computable General Equilibrium
COROS	Common Objectives and Requirements of Organic Standards
COVID-19	CoronaVirus Disease of 2019
CS	Case Study
CTEO	Chief Trade Enforcement Officer
DSB	Dispute Settlement Body
EAOPS	East African Organic Products Standard
EBA	Everything but Arms
EEA	European Economic Area
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EGD	European Green Deal
EPA	Economic Partnership Agreement
ERS	Economic Research Service
EU	European Union
F2F	Farm to Fork
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
FIBL	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture
FTA	Free Trade Agreement
G20	Group of Twenty
GFI	Gross Farm Income
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GOMA	Global Organic Market Access
GSP	Generalised Scheme of Preferences
GSP+	Generalised Scheme of Preferences Plus
GTAP-AEZ	Global Trade Analysis Project – AgroEcological Zones
IFOAM	International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements
ILO	International Labour Organisation
IT	Information Technology
ITF	International Task Force
ITRIn	Index Global Food System TRIPTOLEMOS Index
JRC	Joint Research Centre

LDCs	Least Developed Countries
LULUCF	Land-Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry
MAR	Market Access Regulation
MATS	Making Agricultural Trade Sustainable
MEA	Multilateral Environmental Agreement
MRL	Maximum Residue Level
NTM	Non-Tariff Measure
OCTs	Overseas Countries and Territories
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OSA	Open Strategic Autonomy
PCSD	Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development
POS	Pacific Organic Standard
PPM	Process and Production Methods
SADC EPA	Southern African Development Community Economic Partnership Agreement
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SEP	Single Entry Point
SIA	Sustainability Impact Assessment
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SPS	Sanitary and Phytosanitary
SSA	Sub-Saharan Africa
TBT	Technical Barriers to Trade
TRIPS	Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights
TSD	Trade and Sustainable Development
UAA	Utilized Agriculture Area
UN	United Nations
UNCTAD	United Nations Conference on Trade and Development
USDA	United States Department of Agriculture
USSR	Union of Soviet Socialist Republics
VAT	Value Added Tax
WTO	World Trade Organisation

1. INTRODUCTION

The present work is part of the Making Agricultural Trade Sustainable (MATS) project that explores what changes have to be made to agricultural and trade policies to achieve sustainable outcomes. This discussion paper pursues an improved understanding of the coherence of European Union (EU) policy frameworks with respect to their impacts on Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and global agreements on environmental and climate challenges. More specifically, it examines the degree of policy coherence between the EU's internal and external policies shaping agricultural trade and the alignment of EU agricultural trade policy and trade agreements in economic, social, and environmental terms.

Policy coherence for sustainable development (PCSD) is an approach and policy tool for integrating the various dimensions of sustainable development at all stages of policymaking. Its main objectives are to increase governments' capacities (i) to foster synergies across economic, social, and environmental policy areas, (ii) to identify trade-offs and reconcile domestic policy objectives with internationally agreed objectives, and (iii) to address the spillovers of domestic policies.

The second section of this discussion paper presents a review of existing studies and policy evaluations. The third section focuses on the provisions of EU trade agreements on sustainability aspects and the agricultural trade/sector. Section 3.1 examines existing trade-related policies already being implemented, while in section 3.2, elements of sustainability in current EU trade policy are explored. This exploration concerns all the agreements and political initiatives that make up the 'core' trade policy of the EU, i.e., 44 "Agreements in place" involving 77 countries/regions and 5 "Agreements being adopted or ratified" involving 25 countries/ regions. A central part of our study was identifying provisions in the trade agreements under consideration, focusing specifically on the agricultural trade/sector concerning sustainability aspects.

When referring to cooperation for Trade and Sustainable Development (TSD) provisions in the examined trade agreements, themes such as the following are taken into consideration: human, cultural, economic, social, health, and environmental best interests of the respective populations and future generations; environmental/ ecological aspects; labour aspects; social/health aspects; market/ trade aspects; sustainable consumption and production.

Our analysis shows that a small number of trade agreements specifically take into consideration in their provisions the environmental impact of agriculture, including issues such as a) the impact on soil and water quality, b) soil erosion and pollution by agricultural chemicals, c) the management of impacts through the use of antibiotics and decontaminants, d) conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity, and e) genetically modified organisms. Also, in several

cases, climate/climate change-related provisions are included in the trade agreements without mentioning the agricultural trade or sector.

The fourth section includes the examination of three policy issues that have been identified within the diversity of policies enacted or initiated by the EU: (i) organic farming certification, (ii) food safety regulations, and (iii) Green Deal and Biodiversity Strategy (BDS) targets. These policies have been based on their importance for international agricultural trade, although not strictly speaking trade policies. Three of the 15 MATS case studies (CS) have been selected to receive feedback on the region- or sector-specific impacts of the policies examined.

CS1 on “Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Uganda and Tanzania” was selected as the first CS relevant to two policies, Organic Certification on the one hand and Food Safety Regulations on the other. CS4 on “Enhancing Access to Export Markets by Sub-Saharan African Countries through Sustainable Investments to Ensure Quality and Quality of Agri-food Commodities: the cases of Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana” was the second CS relevant to two policies, “Organic Certification” on the one hand and “Food Safety Regulations” on the other. Finally, CS6, “Analysis of cocoa and chocolate purchasing practices that could undermine living incomes for cocoa farmers”, was a sectoral one that analysed the whole cocoa market.

A questionnaire was prepared and sent to project partners of the three CSs to get feedback on the role the specific policy is playing in the CS and the sectors concerned. The first task of this exercise was to evaluate the specific policies within the framework of the particular CSs regarding their contribution to achieving the relevant Goals and Targets of the Sustainable Development Agenda 2030. The Task leaders prepared a list of Goals and Targets and sent it to the CS partners for this purpose. Partners were asked to evaluate the policy according to the criteria Griggs et al. (2017) provided. Further, more policy-specific questions were posed to elicit the CS-relevant information necessary to analyse the results. Finally, policy proposals were provided by CS partners.

The Green Deal and BDS targets have been selected as prospective EU policies, i.e., policies that have recently been enacted or are to be enacted soon. This sub-section includes the potential effects of Green Deal and Biodiversity 2030 rules’ integration in Trade agreements; in the latter, three different scenarios are presented (the “EU only scenario”, the “Middle scenario”, and the “global scenario”), followed by the regional distribution of impacts.

The fifth section comprises the conclusions, divided into two parts: first, policy coherence and sustainability issues in EU trade-related policies, and second, policy proposals to increase coherence with sustainable trade; these policy

proposals concern EU organic farming certification scheme, the harmonised food safety regulations for EU imports, and agricultural extension and training.

2. A REVIEW OF EXISTING STUDIES AND POLICY EVALUATIONS

The EU's current view on its trade policy is set out in a comprehensive report entitled 'Trade Policy Review - An Open, Sustainable and Assertive Trade Policy' (**European Commission, 2021**). According to this report, the EU needs a new trade strategy to address the challenges of economic recovery, climate change and environmental degradation, growing international tensions, greater recourse to unilateralism, and its consequences for multilateral institutions. The new strategy will, therefore, further integrate EU trade policy within the economic priorities as reflected in the Green Deal and the European Digital strategy, specify trade policy's role in the post-COVID economic recovery, and support the pursuit of the EU's geopolitical ambitions. As such, it will show how trade policy endorses the EU's Open Strategic Autonomy (OSA). The new strategy aims to establish a new consensus for trade policy based on openness, sustainability, and assertiveness. It reinforces the EU's position as a global champion of open, rules-based trade that is fair and sustainable.

Also, the EU's trade policy needs to focus on three core objectives: supporting the recovery and fundamental transformation of the EU economy in line with its green and digital objectives; shaping global rules for a more sustainable and fairer globalization; increasing the EU's capacity to pursue its interests and enforce its rights, including autonomous actions where needed. To deliver these three objectives, the Commission will focus on (i) Reforming the WTO (World Trade Organization), (ii) Supporting the green transition and promoting responsible and sustainable value chains, (iii) Promoting the digital transition and trade in services, (iv) Strengthening the EU's regulatory impact (v) Deepening EU's partnerships with neighbouring, enlargement countries and Africa (vi) Reinforcing the EU's focus on implementing and enforcing trade agreements and ensuring a level playing field for EU businesses. For each of these areas, the strategy sets out a number of headline actions to be accomplished during the current Commission's mandate.

Moreover, the OSA reflects the EU's desire to chart its course on the global stage, shaping the world through leadership and engagement while preserving its interests and values. OSA foresees making the best possible use of the opportunities of the EU's openness and global engagement while assertively defending the EU's interests, both internally and externally. In essence, the EU will continue working with partners to advance this positive agenda but will work autonomously when necessary.

Furthermore, the EU will remain open to trade and investment. The EU has a strong network of trade agreements (44 "Agreements in place", involving 77 countries/ regions, apart from the EU part of the agreement and 5 "Agreements being adopted or ratified", involving 25 countries/ regions, apart from the EU part of the agreement), and a substantial trade surplus. Across the EU, 35

million jobs depend on trade. Many are high-quality jobs, while competitive gains from global trade have increased wages by 12-fold. There is the potential to build on this solid foundation but to do so, the EU has to look beyond the borders, given that 85% of global growth will occur outside Europe in the next decade. The best way to ensure the EU's prosperity is to keep trading with its international partners rather than turning inward. Indeed, more than ever, there is a need to open trade to support recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic. The EU is and will remain a champion of openness and global cooperation, a global economic power, and a leader in sustainable growth. Nevertheless, being open does not mean being defenceless. The EU will defend itself from unfair trade practices. The EU is built on and needs openness to strengthen resilience and help keep its industries competitive, to make the Single Market more attractive, and to tackle climate change and other environmental challenges. Openness and engagement are strategic choices that lead to more prosperity, competitiveness, and dynamism.

The EU has been and continues to be steadfast in its support for multilateralism and a rules-based international order. The EU wants to update the global rulebook so that its rules consider the profound economic developments in recent decades. Such reform is needed to ensure the stability and predictability necessary for trade to thrive. The EU's new strategy sets out an agenda to reform the WTO by adopting a first set of WTO reforms focusing on sustainable development and working towards mainstreaming sustainability in the work of the Organization, reinforcing WTO rules against negative spill-overs of state intervention in member economies.

In addition, the EU intends to intensify its engagement with Africa and its neighbouring countries, including enlargement countries, and to consolidate its partnerships with key growth regions, notably Latin America and Asia-Pacific. Finally, the transatlantic relationship is the world's most significant and economically important partnership. It is deeply rooted in shared interests and values. It is essential to work with the US administration to reform the WTO by reinforcing its capacity to tackle competitive distortions and contribute to sustainable development. It also offers new prospects to cooperate closely on both economies' green and digital transformation.

The EU is crucial in promoting a transition to sustainable and resilient food systems, with its ambitious Green Deal and global role in agri-food markets. While examining the application of EU health and environmental standards to imported agricultural and agri-food products, the **European Commission (2022a)** holds that the COVID-19 crisis and Russia's invasion of Ukraine have exposed vulnerabilities in agricultural and food systems, necessitating a shift towards a sustainable and resilient EU food system. The EU's ambitious health, environmental, and sustainability standards contribute to achieving legitimate global concerns, aligning with the 'One Health' approach. To enhance and promote health and environmental standards, the EU will continue its efforts at a

multilateral level, intensifying its efforts and fostering better coordination and synergies.

Trade agreements and bilateral cooperation offer opportunities to achieve sustainability standards with partner countries. The EU has already made progress in this area with its ambitious trade agenda, including a TSD chapter and provisions on cooperation on animal welfare and AMR (Antimicrobial Resistance), while a Sustainable Food Systems chapter is proposed in future agreements.

Considering trade impacts on third countries, the EU will ensure the coherence of its sustainability agenda with its enlargement, neighbourhood, and development policies. Flanking measures, including funding, technical cooperation, and capacity building, may assist trading partners in engaging in more sustainable practices, especially for vulnerable countries and neighbouring partners undertaking ambitious commitments in those fields.

The EU can take measures autonomously to address global environmental concerns or animal welfare issues when necessary. However, applying Process and Production Method (PPM) regulations to imported products must be done in full respect of WTO rules and international commitments. Measures considered illegitimate or protectionist and inconsistent with the EU's international obligations and rights may expose the EU to a risk of retaliation.

Regulatory proposals need to undergo a case-by-case assessment of their WTO compatibility. Each case must be carefully analysed on its merits, considering control mechanisms' technical and economic feasibility. The feasibility and proportionality of adequate means to control and enforce these measures must be assessed in relation to the costs and benefits of doing so.

The coherence of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) with the Green Deal and trade policy is crucial for farmers' economic growth, competitiveness, and environmental performance. However, as the **European Commission (2022b)** stresses, concerns have arisen that the Farm to Fork (F2F) Strategy may lead to the off-shoring of food and agricultural production overseas, potentially undermining policy objectives. To ensure the F2F Strategy benefits farmers and European society, it is essential to ensure coherence between agricultural, environmental, and trade policies. The AgriFish Council has identified three levels of action: autonomous measures, multilateral actions, and bilateral actions. Autonomous measures can be justified for ethical reasons or to protect global sustainability concerns, but they must comply with WTO rules. Multilateral actions should be promoted in relevant fora, including the FAO (Food and Agriculture Organisation) /Codex, WTO, and G20, while considering the varying levels of development among partners, particularly least-developed countries and middle-income countries. Bilateral actions should be made to foster the EU sustainability agenda and enhance cooperation in sustainable food systems. The

European Commission is working on a report to examine how to achieve coherence between agricultural, environmental, and trade policies.

The Hilton beef quota is a potential example of a sustainable agenda; however, further discussion is needed to ensure its effectiveness with trade partners. The European Commission has made commitments in the Trade Policy Review and F2F Strategy and is working on a report to achieve coherence between agricultural, environmental, and trade policies. The report will assess the rationale and legal feasibility of these approaches.

The CAP has emphasized the importance of improving European agriculture's environmental and climate performance over the past 30 years. The Green Deal strategy aims to facilitate the transition towards sustainable food systems, outlined in the F2F strategies and the Biodiversity Strategies (BDS).

A series of contributions in the recent scientific literature concern the effectiveness of the environmental and climatic performance of the CAP.

A report prepared by the **European Commission, Joint Research Centre, et al. (2021)** contributes to the 2030 Climate Target Plan impact assessment using the CAPRI (Common Agricultural Policy Regionalised Impact) model, which incorporates policies for accelerating the transition towards sustainable food systems. The report presents a modelled scenario of an ambitious implementation of CAP reform proposals, including four quantitative targets from the F2F and BDS strategies. These targets have the most significant potential to affect the agricultural environment and production, and the CAP can provide specific contributions to these targets. The impacts are modelled under three scenarios: a status quo scenario assuming no change in the CAP compared to its implementation during 2014-2020 and a potential implementation of the CAP post-2020 legal proposal targeting these objectives.

However, the report does not constitute an impact assessment of the strategies, as the modelling scope does not include all the strategies' measures that would alter the impacts reported. Other analytical approaches and tools are necessary to arrive at a more complete picture of the potential implications of this transition.

F2F and BDS strategies propose a comprehensive approach, but their inclusion requires additional assumptions and tools to capture positive synergies. The modelling results indicate that reaching four targets under the current CAP implementation achieves significant environmental benefits, such as reductions in greenhouse gases, ammonia emissions, and gross nutrient surplus. However, the extent of these benefits is not fully quantified. The impact on EU production, agricultural product prices, and income can be lowered by about one-fifth when CAP implementation aligns with the 2018 Legal Proposal and targets the transition to more sustainable agriculture. The new CAP implementation also

increases the positive performance of the agricultural sector in environmental terms. The impacts on international markets are limited in both scenarios.

Copenhagen Economics (2016) researchers have studied the impacts of EU trade agreements on the agricultural sector. They claim the EU market is saturated, and 90% of the additional world demand for agri-food products will be generated outside Europe. The Russian ban negatively impacted EU exports, and EU exporters seek new market opportunities. The EU's ambitious bilateral trade agenda is set to continue, with trade agreements creating opportunities for producers and benefiting the EU economy and consumers. However, gains from these agreements should not be taken for granted. This study analysed the EU's trade agreements with Mexico, South Korea, and Switzerland to assess the economic, social, and environmental impacts and identify factors that have fostered and impeded the development of the EU agri-food trade.

The analysis revealed that these trade agreements have increased EU agri-food exports by over 1 billion EUR and increased value added in the sector by 600 million EUR. These agreements have supported nearly 20,000 jobs in the agri-food sector, with 13,700 in primary agriculture. Value added in other sectors has increased by over 400 million EUR, and the agreements have supported an additional 7,700 jobs in the EU. The trade agreements have also increased EU imports and given EU consumers access to cheaper agri-food products. The analysis shows that EU exporters compete more equally against third-country exporters. The EU-Mexico Free Trade Agreement (FTA), which entered into force in 2000, has increased EU exports to Mexico by around EUR 105 million, mainly due to an increased volume of processed agri-food products exported by EU producers before the FTA entered into force. The increase in EU exports to Mexico reflects an increase in total EU exports. The study also found that EU imports from Mexico have increased by around 315 million EUR, mainly due to an increased import volume of primary agricultural products imported from Mexico before the FTA entered into force. The study suggests that the EU-Mexico FTA could be improved by eliminating specific rates and quotas, increasing its scope, reducing tariff peaks, and solving Sanitary and Phytosanitary (SPS) issues on the Mexican side.

The EU-South Korea FTA, which entered into force in 2011, has reversed the negative trend in the EU's market share in South Korea since 2005. The FTA has increased EU exports to South Korea by around 440 million EUR, mainly due to an increased export volume of primary agricultural products. The increase in EU imports from South Korea has not taken place at the expense of intra-EU trade, and the increased imports have had little impact on production in the EU, taking the absolute value into account. The EU-South Korea FTA supported around 15,000 jobs in the EU agri-food supply chain between 2011-2015, mainly in primary agriculture. The agreement is the most ambitious ever implemented by the EU, and its impact will likely grow in the next decade.

The EU-Switzerland trade agreements have increased EU exports to Switzerland by around 530 million euros, mainly due to an increased export volume of processed agri-food products. The increase in EU imports from Switzerland has not occurred at the expense of intra-EU trade, and the increased EU imports from Switzerland have not impacted agri-food production in the EU. The trade agreements have given EU consumers access to more agri-food products at lower prices, mainly in processed food and beverages. However, the increase in EU imports is more significant than the increase in exports measured in absolute and relative terms, likely due to non-zero preferential rates on the Swiss side, making EU agri-food products more expensive in the Swiss market.

The EU-Switzerland trade agreements may have evolved over the past 10-15 years, potentially reducing preferential rates and increasing product coverage. The EU agri-food sector can benefit more from completed trade agreements. EU exporters must build reputations and establish distribution networks before entering new markets. Common EU promotion campaigns and targeted export strategies are crucial for Small and Medium Enterprise (SME) exporters. However, EU exporters are not always aware of trade potentials in new agreements, and joint information campaigns can help them anticipate changing business conditions and implement appropriate commercial strategies. The study highlights the potential of exports to Asian export markets, where demand for high-quality agri-food products and limited domestic production capacity offer new business opportunities for innovative EU companies.

Blot and Kettunen (2021) are sceptical about the efficiency of the new EU trade policy strategy, which focuses on supporting sustainable value chains and setting global standards, promoting the green transition through trade. It includes policy initiatives to stimulate greening, such as liberalizing trade in sustainable goods and services and using sustainability standards throughout value chains. The EU is committed to proactively pioneering new international regulations and standards for green and digital transitions with EU standard-setting bodies. However, the success of these initiatives depends on the coherent regime of individual initiatives, which must deliver the best overall outcome for climate and the environment. The strategy does not address the need for synergies between internal and external policies shaping trade and does not address the importance of existing initiatives like appointing a Chief Trade Enforcement Officer (CTEO) and establishing a Single Entry Point (SEP).

Triptolemos.org (2021) has examined the consequences of the Green Deal from the perspective of a sustainable global food system since its potential impact on all links in the food chain makes it potentially very significant. With the aid of 30 researchers from various specialities, it considers not only environmental or economic factors but also cultural, dietary, legal, etc.

The agricultural sector significantly contributes to climate change and can help reduce its impact. The Green Deal aims to address climate change challenges,

population growth, and resource scarcity, but it faces socio-economic risks. A prior systematic evaluation of these risks and their impact on economic sectors and consumers is necessary, especially for vulnerable populations. The EU27 has a food energy self-sufficiency of 105%, which could lead to agricultural production turning a low surplus into a deficit. This could increase the need for imports from third countries, which may not follow the principles set by the EU in its Green Deal. The Green Deal may become more of a change in forms than the substance of the European agri-food sector if it only proposes a shift in the production system without considering the quantitative and qualitative aspects of farmers and associated sectors. Europe aims to become a world leader in sustainability and competitiveness. Still, the European Commission seems overly optimistic in its approaches. Therefore, it is crucial to maintain and increase efforts in research, innovation, and technology transfer to generate new fundamental knowledge about plant and animal physiology, aiming to improve the productivity and resilience of food systems.

The EU is a significant global player in food security matters, with initiatives such as reforming the CAP and the F2F Strategy. The CAP aims to remunerate farmers for providing environmental services and reduce the impact of agrochemicals. The F2F Strategy focuses on a food chain perspective, promoting healthier diets, reducing losses and waste, and applying circular economy and bioeconomy principles. However, it also faces challenges such as the risk of a double food system and the impact on the population, with 17% of the European population living in extreme poverty and 40% being overweight. The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the importance of a sustainable, robust, and resilient European food system. The Green Deal's measures may severely impact production structures, reducing production and increasing costs and impacting exports and global food security. European foods, known for their safety, nutrition, and quality, now aspire to be the world benchmark for sustainability. However, the environmental ambition of the Green Deal cannot be achieved alone, as climate change and biodiversity loss are global. The Triptolemos Foundation has developed a model for quantifying and analysing the impact of the Green Deal on a sustainable global food system, known as the ITRIn Index.

A group of trade unions, farmers, business owners, engaged citizens, and organizations working in the environment, consumption, development, and research fields have formed the 'Trade Differently' coalition. In one of their articles (**Geurts et al., 2021**), they outline possible scenarios for fair and environmentally responsible trade policy and the steps that should be taken to achieve them. They also claim that CAP, after 1995, abandoned stable, remunerative prices for agrarian products. This policy has led to overproduction and volatile prices for European farmers. The EU has abandoned supply management for milk and sugar, causing local farmers to suffer while multinational agribusiness profits from low agricultural prices. The EU also uses millions of hectares of land in the Global South to produce luxury products like

biofuels, beef, and cattle feed, destroying nature and leading to indigenism and loss of land for small-scale farmers and peasants. The planned reform of the CAP after 2021 presents an opportunity to break with neoliberal aberrations and promote food sovereignty in agricultural trade. This would enable every region, including the EU, to produce food sustainably through its farmers and population.

Producers of perishable plant crops and fishers may unite in producer organizations, preventing monopolies and reducing the difference between consumer and farmer prices. Minimum prices will apply for supermarket products, and 'lowest price guarantees' will be banned. According to these authors, the reform of the CAP should ensure farmers receive prices that cover their costs, allowing for the discontinuation of the current general EU subsidy per hectare. However, farmers who deliver services in line with climate, biodiversity, landscape, and nature objectives will receive cost-covering fees. Product subsidies for cultivating crops with lower selling prices will be implemented, deploying the 59 billion EUR annual CAP budget more effectively. Financial incentives for healthier food will be introduced, such as a national tax on meat and sugar and a 0% VAT tariff on healthy products like vegetables and fruit. If these measures lead to excessive food prices for the poorest, the government will increase social benefits and minimal wages.

The CAP has emphasized the need to improve European agriculture's environmental and climate performance, while the Green Deal strategy aims to facilitate the transition towards sustainable food systems, linking all actors in the system. Thus, **Barreiro Hurlé et al. (2021)** have studied the EU's 2030 Climate Target Plan impact assessment using the CAPRI model, which incorporates policies for accelerating the transition towards sustainable food systems. The analysis includes reducing pesticide use, nutrient surplus, organic farming, and high-diversity landscape features. The impacts are modelled under three scenarios: a status quo scenario, assuming no change in the CAP, and a potential implementation of the CAP post-2020 legal proposal. However, the report does not constitute an impact assessment of the strategies, and additional analytical approaches and tools are needed to capture the full potential impacts of the transition.

The potential to further reduce these impacts is underestimated by not considering all initiatives, measures, and resulting synergies covered by the strategies. For example, the shift to organic agriculture could mitigate production reductions, lower livestock production could have less impact on prices and trade, and the positive impact could be enhanced via accelerated technological development and efficiency improvements.

The exercise assumes that the EU acts alone, which could lead to emissions leakage to other world regions. However, non-EU countries have committed to reducing GHG emissions, which could reduce the leakage and negative impacts

for the EU. The report does not provide information on all the benefits derived from those targets for the agricultural sector and broader society.

The analysis on the supply side of sustainable food systems needs improvements to capture the positive feedback in yields from enhanced ecosystem services provided by improved biodiversity. Additional measures could be introduced to reduce the environmental impact of production, minimizing the trade-off between meeting targets and production impacts. The assumptions about the impacts on farm management and yields of the reduction in pesticide use and the increase in organic farming do not capture potential beneficial side effects beyond the agricultural sector, such as health benefits. The Commission's proposal to move from a farm accountancy data network to a farm sustainability data network will help address these limitations. On the demand side, the analysis does not incorporate the ambition related to food waste reduction, the move towards different diets, or the promotion of organic and sustainably produced food. Data availability is an issue that requires cooperation between the retail and processing industries. The Joint Research Centre (JRC) is working to improve knowledge of the effects of measures implemented, develop models to improve the representation of pesticides and organic farming and explore avenues to incorporate the impact of food waste reductions and diet changes. A comprehensive assessment should also incorporate a complete food systems approach incorporating other phases of the food value chain and changes in consumer preferences and behaviour.

The proposed legislative framework for sustainable food systems will necessitate a comprehensive impact assessment to evaluate the EU's agricultural sector's environmental, climate, and health performance. Agroeconomic models will be used, but the current approach fails to capture the positive synergies associated with a better environment. The current model focuses on past trade-offs between environmental protection and agricultural production, failing to capture the positive synergies associated with a better environment. Further research and analysis can help improve the model's capacity to capture targets and estimate benefits, highlighting the need for further research and analysis.

The Grain Club has commissioned a study (**Henning and Witzke, 2021**) to analyse the effects of the F2F Strategy on the production, consumption, and trade of relevant agricultural products within the EU, with a particular focus on Germany. The analysis was carried out using the CAPRI model, a regionalized partial equilibrium model centred on the agricultural sector, and considers the effects of farm production on the environment and land use. The CAPRI sector model is connected to an international trading model to consider global trade flows and the effects on agricultural prices. The trading model is based on the new trade theory, which holds that traded agricultural commodities are imperfect substitutes rather than perfectly homogeneous goods. As a result, trade in agricultural commodities has non-linear transaction costs and trade flows.

According to the study results, the F2F Strategy would lead to a significant decline in production and a respective price increase within the EU, with the reduction of the N-balances by 50% generating the most substantial effects. Compared to the price increase within the EU, the price increases for non-EU countries are much more moderate; in the EU, mineral fertilizer per hectare (ha) and pesticides per ha are strongly reduced by -51% and -58%, respectively. Concerning land use, the implementation of the F2F Strategy, by definition, implies a strong growth of set-aside and ecological priority areas by +11 Million ha. However, implementing the F2F Strategy also implies a transformation of 1.5 Million ha of forest land into Utilized Agriculture Area (UAA).

The F2F measures will significantly increase the ecosystem services of all EU member states and lead to public adjustment costs of approximately 42 billion EUR, of which the significant share would be financed by consumers, in contrast to the farmers' income, which is expected to increase by up to +35 billion EUR. Increasing agricultural income can be explained by the very inelastic demand for agricultural products and the low reactivity of agricultural trading. The F2F adjustment costs are distributed asymmetrically between consumers and farmers and among the farmers themselves; less competitive farms would completely give up production, and more competitive farms survive to collect the higher profits from higher farm prices while exiting farms would realize a loss. In contrast to farmers, agricultural processing industries face a decrease in value-added by the F2F strategy, varying from -0.02% up to -26.9%, depending on the industry. F2F causes food security, poverty, or biodiversity changes in non-EU countries relevant to European society. The most substantial leakage effects can be observed within animal production.

The study of **Henning and Witzke (2021)** reveals that a decrease in European agriculture production reduces net exports by the EU, particularly for cereals and beef. If all F2F measures are implemented simultaneously, the EU net export position for these products would revert to a net import position. However, this would only apply to poultry, while the net milk export would remain unchanged. The net export of pork would also be reduced, and the respective net import values for cereals and beef would increase. The welfare effects of the F2F Strategy depend on the responsiveness of agricultural trading. Increased responsiveness of agricultural trading implies a fundamental redistribution of adjustment costs between farmers and consumers and significantly increased leakage-effects. The price, trade balance, and welfare effects depend on including the European agricultural market in international agricultural trade. If perfect responsiveness is assumed, the costs of implementing the F2F Strategy would be borne by farmers, leading to a more considerable reallocation of production and additional GHG-emissions in non-EU countries. Reducing European meat consumption significantly reduces leakage effects, while general food waste reduction in European food supply chains can positively impact

leakage effects. Including agriculture in CO₂-allowance trading increases the climate efficacy of the F2F Strategy.

In this study (i.e., **Henning and Witzke, 2021**), the EU's F2F measures were ad hoc and lacked a specific scientific foundation. The Green Deal's goals include reducing nitrogen pollution, climate neutrality, and conserving biodiversity. Agricultural production, or rather consumption of agricultural goods, plays a crucial role in achieving these goals. Current agricultural production and consumption patterns do not align with the Green Deal's objectives and require adaptation. A common European agricultural framework is needed to achieve these modifications.

The study has identified several key issues that the F2F Strategy has to address. Firstly, it is ineffective in reducing climate change, particularly regarding GHG emissions. The strategy should promote technological progress in the agricultural sector to minimize leakage effects, reduce food waste, and avoid production shifts to non-EU countries. Secondly, it should include the LULUCF-Sector (Land-Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry), which accounts for 48% of the compensation for the F2F-induced reduction of GHG emissions in agriculture. Controlling LULUCF effects in the EU is relatively easy through regulatory measures and proven incentives for land-use change. Thirdly, the strategy's actions should be goal-oriented, with political restrictions targeting ecosystem services provided by agriculture. Lastly, the strategy needs to ensure a socially just distribution of adjustment costs, ensuring that all member states implement all cornerstones and that costs and benefits are distributed fairly among farmers and consumers. Further research is needed to identify adequate indicators and incentive schemes for effective public management of biodiversity.

Finally, the Green Deal goals require smart and innovative governance mechanisms that combine market flexibility and planning security with regulatory policy interventions. These mechanisms should allow for flexible adaptation of regional and temporal distribution of costs and benefits to changing framework conditions. Tradable allowances (emissions trading systems) for CO₂ emissions in the non-agricultural sector are promising tools for monitoring ecosystem services like N-balance and biodiversity. These systems also allow for a flexible and transparent division of costs between farmers and consumers and between individual social groups.

The EU Green Deal aims to develop an environment-friendly and healthy food system, affecting European producers' competitive position and international trade in foodstuffs. In order to help resolve sustainability issues in trade policy, intending to promote coherence between agriculture, trade, and Green Deal policies, the EU has proposed legislation and other initiatives. Thus, in a recent report, **Matthews (2022)** examines the impact of measures taken to implement this objective in the agri-food sector on developing countries, particularly low-income developing countries, and suggests ways to avoid

negative impacts that might hinder their progress toward the UN 2030 SDGs. The French Presidency of the EU Council of Ministers (during the first half of 2022) set priorities to encourage discussions on reciprocal environmental and health standards for European products and imported products, prioritizing the introduction of sectoral mirror clauses and regulation on deforestation-free imports. These priorities are built on previous EU Trade Policy Reviews and legislative packages for the future CAP. These policies aim to safeguard EU production capacity, avoid off-shore negative environmental consequences, and raise global sustainability standards. Mirror clauses are an example of a unilateral measure, but their use has been discussed mainly at a conceptual level. Choosing the most appropriate trade policy instrument in a specific context should be based on comparing different measures' benefit/risk ratios. The study concludes that mirror clauses may be an appropriate instrument in certain circumstances, but their relevance should be decided on a case-by-case basis, taking the following six principles into account:

- Is the level-playing field argument justified?
- How effective is the measure in raising sustainability standards in third countries?
- Which sustainability requirements are relevant?
- Are the sustainability risks evaluated differently in different countries?
- Who bears the cost of a mirror clause?
- What are the risks of retaliation?

Legal basis, political commitment, and demand from civil society exist for EU trade relations in general, and its bilateral trade agreements in particular, to support the achievement of the SDGs internally and to deliver sustainability globally. However, according to **Blot et al. (2022)**, recent studies show that the EU generally outsources economic, social, and environmental impacts abroad, notably through trade. There is, therefore, an urgent need to make EU trade and its impacts on global value chains more sustainable. Improving EU FTAs regarding the scope of their sustainability commitments and monitoring and enforcement mechanisms is a crucial part of that objective as they encompass a large share of EU trade.

This report takes stock of the current status of the EU trade policy before looking at case studies to illustrate specific issues identified. It concludes by proposing three sets of recommendations for EU bilateral trade to make a positive contribution to sustainability globally:

1. Trade SIAs (Sustainability Impact Assessments) and Ex-post assessment processes
 - SIAs and Ex-post assessments are systematic and correlated to specific milestones of the FTA negotiations and implementation.
 - Co-ownership of SIAs between relevant Directorate-General.

- Flanking measures to CGE (Computable General Equilibrium) modelling.
- 'Triggers' clause to initiate a review of an agreement.
- Involvement of trade partner countries in Ex-post assessments.

2. FTA TSD Chapters

- "Tailor-made" TSD chapters for each trade agreement.
- Stronger Language in TSD provisions.
- A binding framework to evaluate actual progress on commitments.
- MEAs (Multilateral Environmental Agreements) upgraded as essential elements.
- Development of a Rapid Response Mechanism under FTAs.
- Effective TSD dispute settlement process.
- CTEO and SEP to address TSD complaints effectively.
- Involvement of empowered civil society throughout the process.

3. Unboxing sustainability from TSD Chapters

- Pre-agreement commitments.
- Provisions throughout FTA for sustainable trade (i.e., differentiated tariffs, bans of harmful trade, etc.).
- Financial support linked to sustainability commitments.
- Alignment between FTA provisions and EU trade-related domestic measures.
- Improve the capacity to review existing FTAs.

Several policy goals in the EU F2F strategy impact agricultural production within and outside the EU. **Wesseler (2022)** discusses the potential effects from an economic angle. By taking into account only partially quantified benefits and costs, he draws on economic evaluations by other authors and discusses their broader implications. Overall, the analyses point to a quantitative decline in EU agricultural production. The F2F strategy harms total consumer surplus and, depending on the underlying assumptions, either causes a net increase or decrease in producer surplus, leading to a net loss in overall welfare. Benefits and costs associated with the F2F strategy's environmental effects, such as those on GHG emissions, biodiversity, or the landscape, are partially quantified. Because of this, policymakers have implicitly determined that the additional net benefits outweigh the reductions in consumer surplus by implementing the strategy. Without additional technological and institutional changes, such as promoting the application of contemporary biotechnology by lowering regulatory barriers, the economic studies combined with studies on the impact of agricultural practices on biodiversity and the emission of greenhouse gases do not support this claim. It is also uncertain whether the majority of consumers will hold this opinion. It is up to EU policymakers to put the required institutional changes into place.

Furthermore, **Guyomard et al. (2023)** postulate that the new CAP for the 2023-2027 timespan, like its predecessors, will fall short of producing substantial climatic and environmental gains. They demonstrate how the three instruments of conditionality, eco-schemes, and agri-environment and climate measures may have been deployed more consistently and productively in the policy's green architecture. Their recommendations are founded on the fundamental ideas of fiscal federalism and public economics, as well as on agronomy and ecological research findings. The minimum standards that each and every agricultural producer must achieve are known as conditionality criteria. Farmers should be rewarded for efforts that go above and beyond these fundamental needs through eco-schemes for global public goods supplemented by agri-environment and climate policies focused on local public goods. By focusing on permanent grasslands, crop diversity, green cover, and unproductive agro-ecological infrastructures, eco-schemes should span the whole agricultural region. They also talk about the trade-offs that these ideas could cause.

3. EU TRADE AGREEMENTS: PROVISIONS ON SUSTAINABILITY ASPECTS AND THE AGRICULTURAL TRADE/SECTOR

3.1 Existing trade-related policies, already being implemented

Several agreements and political initiatives make up the 'core' trade policy of the EU. Currently, the EU has 44 "Agreements in place", involving 77 countries/regions and 5 "Agreements being adopted or ratified", involving 25 countries/regions.

There are various types of these agreements:

- **Free trade agreements (FTAs)** enable reciprocal market opening with developed countries and emerging economies by granting preferential access to markets.
- **Economic partnership agreements (EPAs)** are a particular type of FTAs. EPAs are trade and development arrangements between the EU and the African, Caribbean, and Pacific (ACP) countries - designed to facilitate the ACPs' integration into the world economy through gradual trade liberalisation and improved trade-related cooperation.
- **Association agreements (AAs)** strengthen broader political agreements. For example, the deals with Ukraine and Georgia aim to deepen political ties and strengthen economic links with the two countries.
- **Customs Union deals** with Turkey, Andorra, and San Marino. The Customs Unions provide free movement of goods between the two parts of the customs union, alignment on external tariffs, harmonised commercial policy measures, common standards, mutual assistance in customs matters, and cooperation in other fields.
- **The Comprehensive and Economic Trade Agreement (CETA)** is a trade deal between the EU and Canada. It aims to boost trade and help generate growth and jobs. CETA lowers customs tariffs and other barriers to trade between the EU and Canada.

In addition, besides EPAs, the EU has special trade arrangements in place in support of **developing countries**:

- **Generalised Scheme of Preferences (GSP):** The EU offers its current GSP to low and lower-middle-income countries under several multilateral and bilateral agreements and by unilateral waivers. The scheme partially or fully removes EU customs duties for many products coming into the EU market.

- **Generalised Scheme of Preferences Plus (GSP+):** This is a special incentive arrangement for sustainable development and good governance. It cuts EU import customs tariffs to 0% for vulnerable low and lower-middle-income countries that implement 27 international conventions related to human rights, labour rights, protection of the environment, and good governance.
- **Everything but Arms (EBA):** a special arrangement for least developed countries, which grants full duty-free and quota-free access to the EU Single Market for all products except arms and armament.

It has to be noted that some clarifications about tariff quotas are provided in Annex I.

Other specific trade arrangements include:

- **Market Access Regulation (MAR):** it provides duty-free quota-free access to the EU market for products originating in those ACP countries that do not benefit from an EBA regime and have concluded EPAs pending ratification.
- **European Economic Area (EEA):** The EEA brings the 27 EU member states and three European Free Trade Association (EFTA) nations - Iceland, Liechtenstein, and Norway - together in the EU Single Market, guaranteeing the freedom of movement for goods, services, people and capital, as well as unified related policies (competition, transport, energy, economic and monetary cooperation).
- **Overseas Countries and Territories (OCTs):** The OCTs are not part of the European Community territory but are constitutionally linked to three Member States (Denmark, France, and the Netherlands). The European Community grants unilateral trade preferences to all products originating in the OCTs, aiming to promote their economic and social development and establish close economic relations between them and the Community.

International agricultural trade is also strongly affected by the **World Trade Organisation (WTO) Agreement on Agriculture (AoA)**, which came into force on 1 January 1995, making a decisive move towards the objective of increased market orientation in agricultural trade. The AoA includes four main parts: the AoA itself; the concessions and commitments Members undertake on market access, domestic support, and export subsidies; the Agreement on SPS Measures; and the Ministerial Decision concerning Least-Developed and Net Food-Importing Developing countries.

On the basis of the AoA, WTO Member States undertook to implement **an agricultural policy reform agenda** that lays down specific binding commitments in three major areas: market access, domestic support, and export subsidies. In addition, some provisions of the Agreement on the

Application of **Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures (SPS)** also involve agricultural production and trade; this agreement sets out the basic rules on food safety and animal and plant health standards that governments must follow. Also, the AoA provisions are supplemented by the Agreement on Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) and technical assistance mechanisms. SPS and TBT seek to identify how to meet the need to apply standards while avoiding disguised protectionism. Furthermore, **the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS)** involves agricultural trade and production through the protection of geographical designations, a sector of major importance for European agriculture.

Finally, the AoA includes a **Dispute Settlement Body (DSB)** with a stringent dispute procedure, ensuring that signatory states comply with the new multilateral rules.

The Agreement also considers **non-trade concerns**, including food security and the need to protect the environment. It provides special and differential treatment for developing countries, including improving the opportunities and terms of access for agricultural products of particular export interest to these Members. It has to be noted that these agreements contain a certain degree of **flexibility** regarding their implementation by developing countries, WTO members (special and differential treatment), Least Developed Countries (LDCs), and net food-importing developing countries (special provisions).

Within the debate on EU food safety and environmental standards, one of the concerns of the EU, since 2021-2022, is the willingness to introduce reciprocity in agri-food trade agreements, known as '**mirror clauses**'. Mirror clauses, which require all EU trading partners to adhere to the same or similar environmental and sustainability standards as the EU, are an example of a unilateral measure.

As mirror clauses are intended to ensure that imported goods are produced following the same sanitary, phytosanitary, welfare, and environmental standards as those imposed on domestic goods within the EU, their introduction has clear implications for **Process and Production Methods (PPMs)**. When a nation's trade policy is driven by a desire to ensure that imports have been produced in a way that complies with a national or international production or process norm, production and processing methods are used. These norms frequently have an environmental component.

3.2 Aspects of sustainability in current trade policy

EU's trade relationships were examined by country/region to identify the provisions in the relevant trade agreements concerning sustainability within agricultural trade -or sector in general. To do so, the list of agreements provided by the European Commission was taken into account; the complete list of

agreements is available at https://policy.trade.ec.europa.eu/eu-trade-relationships-country-and-region/negotiations-and-agreements_en (EU trade relationships by country/region -> Negotiations and agreements). In specific, 44 "Agreements in place" (involving 77 countries/ regions, apart from the EU part of the agreement) and 5 "Agreements being adopted or ratified" (involving 25 countries/ regions, apart from the EU part of the agreement) were taken into consideration. It should be noted that the "Agreements being negotiated" were not considered in this study.

As a first indication, it could be noted that the majority of the trade agreements include some general provisions (not agricultural-focused) concerning the economic cooperation policies between the two parts (i.e., the EU and the corresponding country/region) on sustainable development, taking into consideration the economic, environmental, and social dimensions of sustainability (in specific, among all cases examined, less than 10% of the agreements do not include any sustainability-focused provisions; most of these agreements are formed and applied prior to 2000). The specific text may differ among the Agreements (in many cases, depending on the timeframe of the Agreement, i.e., when the Agreement was shaped); however, a typical example of such a provision, coming from the Agreement with Albania, is the following (Article 86 - Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Albania, of the other part; In force since 2009): "*Policies and other measures shall be designed to bring about sustainable economic and social development of Albania. These policies should ensure that environmental considerations are also fully incorporated from the outset and that they are linked to the requirements of harmonious social development*". Another example that could be quoted is that from the agreement with the SADC EPA States (Article 6 - Economic Partnership Agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and the SADC EPA States, of the other part; Provisionally applied since 2016-2019, depending on the SADC State): "*The Parties reaffirm their commitments to promote the development of international trade in such a way as to contribute to the objective of sustainable development, in its three pillars (economic development, social development, and environmental protection) for the welfare of present and future generations, and will strive to ensure that this objective is integrated and reflected at every level of their trade relationship*". In brief, when referring to (cooperation for) TSD provisions in the examined trade agreements, themes such as the following are taken into consideration; it should be noted that the themes differ significantly among the examined agreements:

- In general, human, cultural, economic, social, health, and environmental best interests of the respective populations and future generations;
- **Environmental/ ecological aspects:** climate change; low carbon technologies; energy efficiency; (sustainable use of) biological diversity;

preserved natural resources; management of forests; forestry certification schemes and traceability of different forestry products; sustainable fishing practices; combating illegal trade with environmental relevance;

- **Labour aspects:** International Labour Organisation (ILO) Decent Work Agenda; Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work (freedom of association and collective bargaining, forced labour, child labour, no employment discrimination); workers' rights; minimum living wage health and safety at work; labour market adjustment; labour standards; interlinkages between trade and productive employment; labour statistics; human resources development; and lifelong learning;
- **Social/ health aspects:** social protection; social inclusion; freedom; human dignity; social justice; security and non-discrimination; gender equality; social dialogue; public health; reduction and eradication of poverty;
- **Market/ trade aspects:** corporate social responsibility and accountability; private and public certification; sustainability assurance schemes/ labelling and marketing initiatives (e.g., fair and ethical trade, eco-labelling, green public procurement); development of rural and urban micro, SMEs; customs cooperation;
- **Sustainable consumption and production:** circular economy; economic models increasing resource efficiency; reduction of waste generation; sustainability of food systems.

Following the general provisions on sustainable development, the trade agreements include provisions specifying the cooperation policies relevant to sustainability's economic, environmental, and social aspects. With our focus on the agricultural sector, it is worth noting that a small number of trade agreements (agreements involving 11 out of the 102 examined countries) specifically take into consideration in their provisions the environmental impact of agriculture, including issues such as a) the impact on soil and water quality, b) soil erosion and pollution by agricultural chemicals, c) the management of impacts through the use of antibiotics and decontaminants, d) conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity, and e) genetically modified organisms. As examples of such provisions, the agreements with North Macedonia (Article 103 - Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, of the other part; In force since 2004), mentioning that "*Cooperation could centre on the following priorities: [...] the environmental impact of agriculture; soil erosion and pollution by agricultural chemicals, ...*", and with Algeria (Article 52 - Euro-Mediterranean association agreement between the European Community and its Members States, of the one part, and the People's Democratic Republic of Algeria, of the other part; In force since 2005),

mentioning that "*Cooperation shall in particular focus on: [...] the impact of agriculture on soil and water quality...*" could be quoted.

Moreover, it is worth highlighting that in several cases (agreements involving 31 out of the 102 countries taken into consideration), provisions focusing on or taking into consideration the aspect of climate/ climate change are also present in the trade agreements, without -however- making a specific mention to the agricultural trade or sector. For example, the Trade Agreement with Kosovo (Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community, of the one part, and Kosovo, of the other part; In force since 2016) includes the phrase "...environmental and climate considerations...", in the general provision on cooperation policies (Article 93), while also including a specific provision taking into consideration climate change (Article 116): "*The Parties shall cooperate with the aim to assist Kosovo to develop its climate policy and mainstream climate consideration in energy, transport, industry, agriculture, education and other relevant policies. [...] The Parties shall cooperate with the aim, should objective circumstances so permit, to assist Kosovo's involvement in global and regional efforts to mitigate and adapt to climate change*". Depending on the agreement, different climate change-related themes are included in the provisions, including:

- Mitigation of climate change;
- Adaptation to climate change;
- Market and non-market approaches to addressing climate change;
- Carbon trading/ global carbon markets;
- Strengthening of carbon market mechanisms;
- Mainstreaming of climate considerations into sector policies;
- Exchange of climate expertise and support for other sectors;
- Awareness raising, education, and training;
- Low-carbon and adaptation technologies, sustainable renewable energy, and energy efficiency;
- Reduction of emissions from deforestation and forest degradation.

Finally, a central part of our study was to identify provisions in the trade agreements under consideration, focusing specifically on the agricultural trade/sector concerning sustainability aspects. Among the 49 agreements examined, 34 included some provision/s focusing on the sustainability aspects of the agricultural trade/sector. A special mention could be made to the Economic Partnership Agreement between the East African Community Partner States (i.e., Burundi, Kenya, Rwanda, Tanzania, and Uganda) and the EU, with its agricultural-related chapter including 18 articles, most of them being relevant to sustainable-related themes. The full texts of the identified provisions are available in Appendix II. In a nutshell, when referring to agricultural trade/sector-related provisions in terms of sustainability aspects, themes such as the following are reflected; as indicated above, the themes differ significantly among the examined agreements:

- **Production/ technical aspects:** improved production, productivity (e.g., seed program, integrated pest management, biotechnologies, disease handling) and diversification; modernisation of infrastructures and equipment (e.g., irrigation facilities, water management); development of packaging, storage, and marketing techniques; capacity-building, infrastructure and technology transfer; exchange of best practices; technical assistance, education, training, and information events; support for research programs; preservation of agricultural traditional knowledge;
- **Financial/ Market aspects:** modernisation, diversification, and restructuring of the agriculture, agro-industrial, and service sectors; development of agri-business; cooperation in the agriculture, forestry, and rural development sectors; increased competitiveness; promotion of agricultural service cooperatives; attention to small scale operations; agricultural financing services (e.g., insurance schemes and instruments for access to finance); improved distribution channels and marketing chains; certification instruments (e.g., electronic certification);
- **Regulatory/ policy aspects:** agricultural and rural development policies; regional CAP; policies aiming to diversify production; policies and legislation on agricultural biotechnology products; food production and marketing quality standards (e.g., standards on agricultural practices, organic and non-genetically modified foods, and geographical indications); sanitary, phytosanitary and veterinary standards; water management, veterinary, plant health, and quality regulations;
- **Environmental/ Ecological aspects:** environmentally sound practices; sustainable management of natural resources; agricultural water resources; environmental health, animal and plant health; protection of animal welfare; forestry sector (i.e., reforestation, forest fire prevention, forest pasture and combating desertification);
- **Social/ health aspects:** food security; poverty eradication; cooperation in health; livelihoods of rural and fishing communities; rural employment; income of farm households; economic well-being for rural communities; sustainable rural development; secured livelihood.

4. SPECIFIC POLICY CASE STUDIES

Three policy issues have been identified within the EU's multiplicity of policies enacted or initiated. These policies have been based on their importance for international agricultural trade, although not strictly speaking trade policies.

Three of the 15 MATS case studies (CS) have been selected to receive feedback on the region or sector-specific impacts of the policies examined.

CS1 on “Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Uganda and Tanzania” was selected as the first CS study relevant to two policies, “Organic Certification” on the one hand and “Food Safety Regulations” on the other. The Tanzanian part of the study deals with 150 smallholders and two estates, while in the Ugandan area, the 546 coffee producers of the 2010/11 campaign have increased to 617 in 2015/16 to reach 554 coffee farms in 2019/20.

Uganda was the African country with the most extended area under organic farming, i.e., more than 505,000 hectares, and the largest number of organic producers, with over 404,000 in 2021. Uganda was followed by Ethiopia (over 332,000 hectares) and Tanzania (almost 287,000 hectares). The most important organic crops are cocoa, olives, coffee, nuts, cotton and oilseeds, and the largest part is exported. From 2018 to 2020, African exports increased by almost 60%.

CS4 on “Enhancing Access to Export Markets by Sub Saharan African (SSA) Countries through Sustainable Investments to Ensure Quality and Quality of Agri-food Commodities: The cases of Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana” was the second CS study relevant to two policies, “Organic Certification” on the one hand and “Food Safety Regulations” on the other.

The following Table gives a brief description of the CS under study.

Country	Crop/Product/Sector	Region/country		
		Area covered (ha)	No of animals	Nr of Farms
Tanzania	Cassava	990	-	1,900,000 ³
Uganda	Banana	2,300,000	-	766,667 ^{4,5}
Ethiopia	Goats	-	52,500,000 ⁶	11,300,000
Ghana	Cocoa	2,300,000	-	850,000 ⁷

³ [Tanzania: National Cassava Development Strategy \(NCDS\) 2020 – 2030 – Kilimo Kwanza](#)

⁴ With average farm size 1.9 ha

⁵ Kilimo Trust, 2012

⁶ Central Statistics Agency [CSA], 2021

⁷ www.cocobod.gh

Finally, the third CS6, “Analysis of cocoa and chocolate purchasing practices that could undermine living incomes for cocoa farmers” was a sectoral one that analysed the whole cocoa market. So, it concerns about 5 million farmers and 12,100 ha worldwide, while 469,659 ha or 4.0% of the total global area was under organic farming in 2023.

A questionnaire was prepared and sent to project partners of the three CSs to get feedback on the role the specific policy is playing in the CS and the sectors concerned.

The first task of this exercise was to evaluate the specific policies within the framework of the specific CSs concerning their contribution to achieving the relevant Goals and Targets of the Sustainable Development Agenda 2030. The Task leaders prepared a list of Goals and Targets and sent it to the CS-related partners for this purpose. Partners were asked to evaluate the policy according to the following criteria provided by **Griggs et al. (2017)** (Figure 1). Further, more policy-specific questions were posed to elicit the relevant CS information necessary to analyse the results. Finally, policy proposals were provided by CS partners.

Figure 1. A Guide to SDG Interactions (Griggs et al., 2017)

4.1 Organic farming certification

Organic farming certification has been selected since, according to the 2023 FIBL (Research Institute of Organic Agriculture) report on organic agriculture worldwide (**Willer et al., 2023**), organic producers reached 3.7 million in 2021 compared to 200,000 in 1999. The countries with the largest number of organic

producers in 2023 were India (1,599,010), Uganda (404,246) and Ethiopia (218,175). Since 2020, there has been a 1.7% overall increase in organic area, with an impressive 17.3% in Africa and 5.8% in Asia, while in Latin America, there was a decrease that could be attributed to the decrease in organic rangeland in Argentina. In 2021, 2.9 million metric tons of organic agri-food products were imported to the EU, an increase of 2.8% since 2020.

4.1.1 The policy context

The EU organic farming certification system is linked with international agricultural trade in three ways. It is described in a specific regulation (EU) 2018/848 chapter on organic production and labelling of organic products and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 834/2007. Accordingly, agrifood products can be imported and traded as organic in the EU if the product complies with the organic farming rules set in the regulation and farmers/processors have been subject to controls by control authorities or control bodies recognised according to a set procedure. These control authorities and/or bodies are recognized as competent to conduct controls in third countries and must provide evidence of their capacity, impartiality and due procedures to fulfil their role. However, there is also the option of organic equivalence. It is a bilateral arrangement between trading partners, recognizing two certification systems as comparable and equally verifiable, allowing for differences (**Jaenicke and Demko, 2015**). Thus, a recognised country is a third country *“which the Union has recognised under a trade agreement as having a system of production meeting the same objectives and principles by applying rules which ensure the same level of assurance of conformity as those of the Union.”* Equivalence is a better option than harmonizing rules and/or regulations since it allows for national/regional adaptations as long as the common objectives are fulfilled and the integrity is assured (Pekdemir, 2018). However, up to now, only 14 countries⁸ have this qualification through bilateral agreements, as far as the EU is concerned.

In order to reduce the certification costs for small farmers, both within the EU and for third countries' producers, the EU has introduced in the latest regulation (EU) 2018/848 the possibility for collective certification schemes under the “group certification” title. Starting from 2022, groups of farmers can be certified collectively provided that their members manage land under a specific threshold of size or the individual certification costs are more than 2% of their turnover or standard output and the economic size of their “organic business” does not exceed certain thresholds. Furthermore, the organic farming land managed by farmers-members should be within geographical proximity, a common marketing system should be established among participants, and, finally, the group must “establish a system for internal controls comprising a documented set of control activities and procedures in accordance with which an identified person or body

⁸ Argentina, Australia, Canada, Chile, Costa Rica, India, Israel, Japan, Tunisia, Republic of Korea, New Zealand, Switzerland, United States of America and the UK

is responsible for verifying compliance with this Regulation of each member of the group". The latter condition is detailed within the same regulation, describing a quite strict "quality assurance" type of scheme.

4.1.2 Impacts on trade

Examining the issue of organic standards and regulation and its effects on organic agriculture trade worldwide, **Vogl et al. (2005)** identify irrefutable benefits derived from the existence of harmonized standards, among others, to increase trust in organic products, facilitation of market access, protection of farmers from unfair competition and consumers from fraud identified. However, they also point out certain caveats, most related to trade and thus are of particular interest in the current discussion. The authors stress the risk of creating new borders and trade barriers while equivalence and harmonization could reduce the leeway for adaptation to local circumstances. Furthermore, discarding local knowledge to homogenise standards under the influence of strong trade partners, i.e., the global North, would provide disincentives for local farmers to innovate to adapt to local circumstances. Thus, valuable local knowledge and experience could be abandoned and lost, and the tendency to cheat increased. The high cost of certification and market access, created by a regulation invasive to the local sociotechnical landscape, could further alienate small farmers from organic and environmentally friendly farming practices. **Vogl et al. (2005)** suggested that harmonisation should not only allow for but should support local adaptations of standards by local farmers' associations. They also suggest the idea of regional standards and quality control systems (recognized by global trade players), with justified differentiation, maintaining their effectiveness in withholding organic farming principles but allowing for adaptations to accommodate regional farming systems. A systematic effort to make the most of local knowledge, land use, farming practices, and social norms is necessary to identify innovations that could have a transformative impact.

Pekdemir (2018) stresses the importance of the TBTs and the application of SPS measures of the WTO for providing the context within which organic regulations/laws/standards are made. Their main aim was to ensure non-discrimination and preclude any unnecessary barriers. After a review of the international institutional landscape regarding organic certification, the author concludes that there is a multiplicity of public, private or hybrid certification systems. The lack of a coherent system of mutual recognition creates a fragmented governance system hindering the uptake of organic standards, hence the expansion of organic farming worldwide, since in many cases, transaction, administrative, and other accompanying costs constitute a burden for farmers, especially heavy for small/family farmers. An important common initiative to disentangle this rather complicated institutional landscape has been the objective of a continuous collaborative project undertaken by the International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements (IFOAM), United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) and FAO. The creation

of an International Task Force (ITF) on Harmonisation and Equivalence in Organic Agriculture from 2003 to 2008, which gave its place to the Global Organic Market Access (GOMA) project, which took place from 2008 up to 2012 resulted in the creation of a benchmark tool for organic standards: Common Objectives and Requirements of Organic Standards (COROS). The process of achieving a common understanding of technical issues concerning the various existing organic certification standards seems to have advanced, as attested by the bilateral agreements signed, e.g., the 14 signed by the EU with third countries. However, apart from the inherently political nature of this process, since it consists only of a broader trade negotiation and agreement, few such agreements have been concluded between developed and developing countries. **Pekdemir (2018)** agrees with the explanation provided by **Bowen and Hoffman (2015)**, who attribute this to the increased need for trust in both parties' technical competence and certification liability. The alternative **Pekdemir (2018)** suggested was to adopt the regionalization of organic standards as a more suitable approach. Regionalisation, in this sense, could take the form of common organic standards and/or equivalence mechanisms or even result in regional agreements involving partners from the public and private sectors of at least two neighbouring countries. The example of the EU organic standards and the benefits of internal organic trade testifies to the success of such an endeavour, even in facilitating trade with third parties.

Apart from decisively promoting intra-regional trade, regional arrangements could enable participant states to negotiate from a better position with significant partners, for example, the EU, in international trade both because of their volume of exports and as a more attractive potential market for exports. Within this context, the author examines, apart from the EU case, six more regional certification initiatives, the East African Organic Products Standard (EAOPS), the Pacific Organic Standard (POS), the Central American initiative, the Asia Regional Organic Standard (AROS), the African Regional Standard (ARS), and lastly, the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) Standard for Organic Agriculture (ASOA). The EAOPS⁹ project, a continuation of a collaborative effort that started in 1997, was initiated with one of the main objectives being to promote trade with major markets, including the EU, by facilitating market access through negotiating equivalence and/or mutual recognition of the standards. This initiative resulted in a regional organic standard that the IFOAM accepted, but the application to the EU for equivalence was unsuccessful. The need for a competent authority for the correct implementation of the standard was stressed within this process. Nevertheless, steps have been taken by EAOPS as well as POS partners towards this direction, i.e., to introduce certification and labelling arrangements, with the Pacific partnership (POS) introducing a Participatory Guarantee System to reduce certification costs for farmers.

⁹ Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda, Burundi, Rwanda

However, the decision of the EU to demand compliance with the EU rules for non-recognized countries and limit the equivalence process only within the framework of a wider bilateral trade agreement forces certification and control organisations to audit and control for compliance to EU rules in the cases where either no such agreement exists, or no specific reference to equivalence is included, thus generating additional costs for organic farmers and exporters, especially for small scale operations.

In conclusion, concerning the EU policy context concerning organic certification as related to trade, one can comment that the options for promoting organic trade with third parties exist within the regulatory framework and institutional arrangements. Nevertheless, at the same time, the restrictive nature of the existing mutual recognition options and the rigidity of the institutional/operational do not allow for local/regional adaptation, not even of the rules affecting production practices and, of course, much less, of the organizational prerequisites. Hence, the possibilities of developing countries and many more small/family farms complying with this set of rules/regulations are scant.

4.1.3 EU organic certification policy and its impact on SDGs at the CS's level

It is worth noting that partners from CS4, "Enhancing Access to Export Markets by SSA Countries through Sustainable Investments to Ensure Quality and Quality of Agri-food Commodities: The cases of Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana" provided distinct evaluations of organic farming depending on the country and the product in question. This allowed an additional comparison. The entire table can be found in Appendix III, which is attached to this document.

The SDG the EU Organic Farming Policy seems to serve is Goal 10, "Reduce inequality within and among countries". Moreover, within this goal, this policy seems to have a significant contribution to target 10.6, "Ensure enhanced representation and voice for developing countries in decision-making in global international economic and financial institutions in order to deliver more effective, credible, accountable and legitimate institutions". Another impressive result is that Goal 12 to "Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns" is the one where EU organic farming certification system contributes to less. It seems that this is because of the widely spread perception (at least among the CS partners) that the EU organic farming policy cancels any effort towards achieving target 12.a "Support developing countries to strengthen their scientific and technological capacity to move towards more sustainable patterns of consumption and production".

One can see that for the CS partners focusing on purchasing practices in the global cocoa/chocolate markets in order to identify risks to undermine the living income of farmers (CS6), the Organic farming policy of the EU is a relatively positive factor in all Goals and Targets that depend on securing a reasonable income for cocoa farmers. On the other hand, for partners focusing on "Reducing

poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Uganda and Tanzania” (CS1), the impact of the EU organic certification scheme and, more specifically, the one that regulates organic imports to the EU, play either an insignificant or enabling role (in the majority of the cases) but not more than that.

Concerning the two most trade-related targets, i.e., 2.b “Correct and prevent trade restrictions and distortions in world agricultural markets, including through the parallel elimination of all forms of agricultural export subsidies and all export measures with equivalent effect, following the mandate of the Doha Development Round” and 2.c “Adopt measures to ensure the proper functioning of food commodity markets and their derivatives and facilitate timely access to market information, including on food reserves, in order to help limit extreme food price volatility” it seems that Organic farming certification as regulated by the EU, has a somewhat positive impact especially in price stabilization.

Finally, an interesting observation is the differences one can see in the evaluation of the partners of the different countries concerning Goal 15. “Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss”. Although most partners agree on the positive contribution of EU organic farming policy towards the sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, the degree of perceived contribution is different.

There seem to be three problems that farmers face when referring to the certification process. The first is that because certification comes from international bodies, partners have identified the risk of a disconnect between the standards/regulations and the local realities. Local conditions, knowledge and experience can be ignored. Furthermore, small producers, often lacking the resources and the capacity, are called to navigate through somewhat burdensome procedures and adopt a new production mentality. The second is the issue of the certification costs, especially for small/family farms. However, it seems that group certification is available and feasible for farmers in all countries. Finally, although there is an extension service, it is not considered adequate even for conventional farms, much less for organic farms facing specific challenges.

4.2 Food safety regulations

4.2.1 The policy context

Regulation 1107/2009 regulates the placement of Plant Protection Products and the relative active substances in the EU market. According to this Regulation, no Plant Protection Product can be traded and used in any Member State unless the active substance(s) contained have been approved and Maximum Residue Levels (MRLs) are set at the EU level. An MRL is the upper legal level of a concentration

for a pesticide residue in or on food or feed set under this Regulation, based on good agricultural practice and the lowest consumer exposure necessary to protect vulnerable consumers according to Regulation 396/2005. This regulation sets the framework for setting MRLs in food and feed. The key aim of the Regulation was to support intracommunity trade in the common market by establishing EU-harmonized MRLs and repealing member-state MRLs. However, when a full MRL is in place at the EU level, this also applies to third-country trade.

According to Reg. 396/2005, an MRL, called Import Tolerance, is set for imported products to meet international trade needs. An Import Tolerance is set when:

- a. The use of the active substance in a plant protection product on a given product is not authorised in the Community for reasons other than public health reasons for the specific product and specific use.
- b. A different level is appropriate because the existing community MRL was set for reasons other than public health reasons for the specific product and specific use.

Hence, one can deduce that an Import Tolerance could be necessary when EU MRLs have not been set for the use of an active substance in a particular crop, or they have been set at a level that creates unnecessary obstacles to trade.

Such cases could be when the product or commodity comes from a crop not grown in the EU, and the existing EU MRL does not satisfy importation needs. There is a multiplicity of circumstances that may cause something like that to occur. For example, the MRL may be very low for a specific crop, or the case that an active substance is approved in the EU, but it is not authorized for use on the particular crop, or an active substance has been withdrawn and hence not allowed in the EU. Due to the regular review of registered active substances, many substances have been withdrawn from the EU markets in the recent years. Some of the substances have been removed for economic reasons (a small market size for the substance within the EU, in conjunction with the costly re-authorisation process, makes supporting this active substance unviable for a company).

4.2.2 Setting import tolerances

All parties demonstrating a legitimate interest in health, including civil society organisations and commercially interested parties such as manufacturers, growers, importers, and producers of products, can apply to set a specific import tolerance. However, as mentioned by the Commission, "due to the data requirements, especially in cases where the active substance has never been notified or authorised in the EU, it is advisable that the producer of the active substance applies for the import tolerance".

New import tolerances for specific uses not authorised in the EU would require an evaluation of data for the specific use, particularly the residue data relevant to the Good Agricultural Practice of that specific use. The decision here is on a case-by-case basis; however, since it depends on the authorisation status of the active substance concerned, the submission and evaluation of active substance data may also be a prerequisite. No more data is usually required if the active substance has already been approved. If the active substance has been previously approved in Europe, the existing dataset will probably provide much of the information needed, possibly needing updating. If, however, the active substance concerned has never been notified, evaluated or authorised in the EU, a complete dataset on toxicology, methods of analysis, and residue behaviour may be required.

4.2.3 Trade-related issues

Ronen (2017) notes that TBT and SPS measures accompanied the reduction and even elimination of tariffs to provide consumers with an increased level of assurance and more accurate information on the quality and safety of food and agricultural products to, eventually, facilitate trade. At the same time, the most common result of imposing such measures is the introduction of compliance costs that act as import levies. **Ronen's (2017)** review of the relevant empirical literature suggests that TBT and SPS's most probable demand effects are harmful, especially for agriculture and food imports from developing countries. **Disdier et al. (2007)** analysed 43 types of measures (out of 115 possible under the WTO rules) notified to the WTO by importing countries. They conclude that the overall impact of SPS measures and TBT on the trade of agricultural products is negative. However, the exports of OECD countries to other OECD countries cannot be considered significant. On the contrary, they conclude that the exports of developing and least developed countries to OECD countries are significantly reduced. According to the authors, this negative impact is exacerbated when only exports from developing and least developed countries to EU member states are considered.

Furthermore, evidence suggests a robust (**International Trade Center, 2021**) but heterogeneous effect of Non-Tariff Measures (NTMs) such as SPS and TBT on food and agricultural-related enterprises, depending mainly on their size (**International Trade Center, 2015**). Thus, small firms active in food exports face particular problems with testing procedures and lengthy inspections. TBT and SPS measures mainly prevent developing countries' exporters from expanding their target markets (**Ronen, 2017**).

Focusing more on MRLs, there is a considerable increase of attention on the weight of MRLs in international food and agricultural products trade. **Hejazi et al. (2022)** report a more than fivefold increase in notifications to WTO concerning food safety and animal/plant health regulations between 2000 and 2019. A report by the **Canada Grains Council (2019)** suggests that according

to WTO, more than 60% of NTM notifications are related to SPS, while 36% of the latter belong to MRLs. **Ferro et al. (2015)** created a standards restrictiveness index and used data on MRLs for 66 agricultural products from 61 importing countries. They conclude that exporting firms from less and least developed countries face more constraints when stricter MRLs are imposed than exporting firms based in developed countries. The primary purpose of setting MRLs is to protect consumers against harmful substances. Although this process, to be compatible with WTO, has to be based strictly on science and sound risk assessment, non-discriminating, and least trade restrictive, there are strong indications that national administrations tend at the same time to use them as protective towards domestic producers. **Li and Beghin (2014)** attempted to identify and estimate the protectionist element in MRLs by comparing individual national MRL standards with those suggested by the Codex Alimentarius, the latter being used to provide a reference level of a non-protectionist approach.

Furthermore, **Jouanjean et al. (2015)** identified interesting spillover effects of MRL implementation in the United States import regimes since they estimated that the probability of a country experiencing at least one import refusal (due to excess residues) is double if there was a refusal of the same product from a neighbouring country in the preceding year. At the same time, they estimated an increase of 62% in the probability of refusal if a related product was refused from the same country.

4.2.4 Aspects of the EU Food Safety Policy and their impacts on SDGs at the CS's level

The evaluation conducted by the CS partners revealed that the SDG most served by the EU food safety measures applied to imports is Goal 2. "End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture", especially Target 2.4: "By 2030, ensure sustainable food production systems and implement resilient agricultural practices that increase productivity and production, that help maintain ecosystems, that strengthen capacity for adaptation to climate change, extreme weather, drought, flooding and other disasters and that progressively improve land and soil quality." While the Goal which the harmonized system for import tolerances contributes is Goal 1. "End poverty in all its forms everywhere", according to the partners from CS1, the import tolerance system is either insignificant or is a constraint in achieving the target "1.1 By 2030, eradicate extreme poverty for all people everywhere, currently measured as people living on less than \$1.25 a day". And of course, there was a common opinion that the SPS measures applied by the EU are indispensable in order to achieve target 12.4 "By 2020 (2030 now), achieve the environmentally sound management of chemicals and all wastes throughout their life cycle, following agreed international frameworks, and significantly reduce their release to air, water and soil in order to minimize their adverse impacts on human health and the environment".

Partners from the CS agree that the existence of a harmonized system of import tolerances as set by the EU facilitates market access and thus promotes sustainable trade, provided, of course, that the information on the specific import tolerance is available and accessible to farmers, especially smallholder farmers.

Partners stress the lack of appropriate extension service as a significant problem, along with more issues identified by the partners of CS1:

- "Limited Access to Information: Farmers may have limited access to information about MRLs and proper pesticide use. Lack of awareness about approved pesticides and their correct application can lead to unintentional violations.
- Inadequate Training and Education: Many farmers may not receive sufficient training on proper pesticide application, safety measures, and the importance of adhering to MRLs. This lack of knowledge can result in the misuse of pesticides, exceeding recommended levels.
- Poor Infrastructure: inadequate infrastructure, including a lack of proper storage facilities and transportation systems, can contribute to the inappropriate handling and storage of pesticides, leading to residue issues.
- Limited Access to Alternatives: Farmers might face challenges accessing and affording safer, alternative pest control methods. Dependence on certain chemical pesticides can increase the risk of exceeding MRLs.
- Lack of Monitoring and Enforcement: Farmers lack effective monitoring and enforcement mechanisms to ensure farmers adhere to MRLs. Without proper oversight, there is a risk of non-compliance going unnoticed.
- Market Access Issues: Farmers might encounter difficulties accessing markets with stringent quality standards. Non-compliance with MRLs can lead to rejected produce, impacting farmers' income and market opportunities.
- Climate Change Effects: Climate change-related challenges, such as unpredictable weather patterns and the spread of new pests and diseases, can complicate pest management strategies, potentially leading to increased pesticide use.
- Financial Constraints: Implementing best practices and acquiring safer pesticides may require financial investments that some farmers cannot afford. This economic barrier can hinder compliance with MRLs."

4.3 Prospective policies (policies that have recently been enacted or are to be enacted soon)

The EU launched the European Green Deal (EGD) in December 2019 in response to environmental and climate challenges. The EGD is a flagship initiative comprising various initiatives, strategies, and legislative acts to allow European society and the economy to undergo an equitable, long-lasting, and inclusive transformation. It covers all sectors, including agriculture and food, through the F2F and the EU BDS for 2030. The EGD aims to build a sustainable and healthier food system, impacting the competitiveness of EU producers and international trade in food. The EU has proposed legislative and other initiatives to address sustainability issues in trade policy and promote coherence between agriculture, trade, and Green Deal policies.

4.3.1 Green deal and biodiversity strategy targets

In this part of the paper, the discussion on the effects of possible integration of the Green Deal and BDS elements in currently under negotiation or future trade agreements is going to focus on the restrictions imposed that are directly linked to agricultural production and, at the same time, offer the possibility to draw quantifiable estimations of the impacts.

The first restriction fulfilling these criteria is the target to reduce nutrient losses in EU agriculture by at least 50% without degrading soil fertility. That is translated into reducing fertilizer use by at least 20% by 2030 (**EC, 2020a**).

The second restriction imposed by the F2F Strategy includes two pesticide-related objectives for 2030. The first is to reduce by 50% the overall use of and risk from chemical pesticides, while the second is to reduce by 50% the use of more hazardous pesticides (**European Commission, 2022c**).

Finally, within the BDS for 2030 (**EC, 2020b**), a target to let at least 10% of agricultural area under high-diversity landscape features has been set to allow wild animals, plants, pollinators and natural pest regulators to thrive. Most of these landscape features are unproductive since they include buffer strips, rotational or non-rotational fallow land, hedges, non-productive trees, terrace walls, and ponds.

It is worth stressing that although these targets are under the prospective policies part of the paper, their partial implementation within the CAP strategic plans has already started, either as obligatory prerequisites for farmers to receive CAP payments, e.g., the obligation to leave at least 4% of arable land under landscape features as part of the enhanced conditionality, or as reduction of input use supported by the -newly introduced in CAP strategic plans- ecoschemes (Reg. EC 2115/2020).

4.3.2. The potential effects of Green Deal and Biodiversity 2030 rules' integration in Trade agreements

A series of articles by an experts' team on behalf of the Economic Research Service (ERS) of the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) (**Beckman et al., 2020; Baquedano et al., 2022; Beckman et al., 2022**) have extensively covered the implications of various adoption scenarios on production levels, market prices, trade as well as on welfare, Gross Domestic Product, Land Use, Gross Farm Income (GFI), Food expenditure and finally Food security. For the study, the authors define a food insecurity indicator as the number of people who lack access to a minimum dietary intake of 2100 kcal daily.

Using the Global Trade Analysis Project – AgroEcological Zones (GTAP-AEZ) model, the authors formulated three scenarios in order to examine the impacts of the adoption of 4 different elements of the subsidies, i.e., 50% pesticide use reduction, 20% chemical fertilizer use reduction, antimicrobial agents use reduction of a 50% and the withdrawal of 10% of the existing agricultural land from productive activities.

Caveats of the approach

In the first of the three scenarios examined, the "EU-only scenario", EU member states, as expected, adopt and implement the strategies, i.e., the four restrictions mentioned above. At the same time, trade is usually permitted without third parties' obligation to comply with the restrictions. Another scenario is the "global scenario", where the restrictions are implemented globally as stipulated by the EU initiative. Finally, the "middle scenario" is where only the EU trade partners depend highly on the EU to implement the rules. In this scenario, a simulation of the consequences of non-adoption is a 50% restriction on imports from non-adopting trade partners.

The authors assume that input restrictions would harm production because additional inputs would be used as replacements, affecting resource allocation. Alternatives to chemical inputs were considered limited due mainly to the seasonal unavailability of labour and the lack of qualified managers. Furthermore, the degree of farmers' readiness to transition to alternatives differs highly among products. When discussing possible changes in land management practices that could mitigate the adverse effects on production, the authors argue that no such adaptations are expected for the time horizon they use (8-10 years).

The "EU-only scenario"

Under this scenario, no obstacles arising from policy restrictions are applied to EU imports. Hence, global agricultural production is reduced by only 1%. For all regions but the EU, an increase in agricultural production is estimated to compensate for the 12% decrease in EU production. The reductions per

commodity in the EU are more pronounced in the cases of oilseeds, wheat and other crops (-61%, -49% and - 41%, respectively).

A direct consequence of the reduced EU production would be an increase in market prices within the EU, and in most cases, more than 10%. In addition, agricultural commodity prices are predicted to increase in all regions and for almost all commodities, firstly because of the increase in EU prices and global demand for domestic products.

International trade is expected to be reduced by 2%, in the case of the EU-only scenario, due to the dominant position of the EU in the international trade of agrifood products. EU imports are expected to increase, while imports from the EU will decline in almost all regions under this scenario. The relatively more favoured products would be other crops, wheat and raw milk, with increases of 31%, 18% and 19%, respectively. EU's largest source of imports is Africa (35% of EU imports); hence, exports to the EU from Africa are expected to rise by 103%. Especially for sugar crops, the increase of exports towards the EU is expected to be 143% for African countries, 127% for India, 146% for Mexico and Central America, 349.1% for Middle Eastern and North African countries and an impressive 1060.7% for other South American states.

Regarding the expected impact of GFI, it seems that apart from the EU, where GFI would undergo a reduction of 16.4%, GFI in all other regions is expected to rise. However, farmers in EFTA countries seem to be the primary beneficiaries, with a 25.8% increase, while the increase in Africa, the Middle East and North Africa, and India is expected to be 3.7 %, 2.6% and 5.3%, respectively.

As estimated through the International Food Security Model (**Zereyesus et al. 2023**), food security is defined as the number of people without access to a 2,100 kcal daily intake, a diet thought necessary to sustain a healthy person. The model generates a baseline against which the impacts of scenarios are assessed. The model in its current state focuses on 83 low- and middle-income countries, and as a baseline in the 2023 edition, it is estimated that in 2023, the food insecure people will be 1.14 billion in the countries covered, which is reduced by 16.8% compared to 2022. The percentage of food insecure population in the 83 low and middle-income countries in focus is estimated to be 26.6%. Finally, under the baseline scenario, 7.9% of these 83 countries' populations are expected to be classified as food insecure in 2033, or 385.9 million persons. That is, a decrease in food insecurity is projected to be 66.1% within the next decade (**Zereyesus et al., 2023**).

Against this optimistic baseline scenario, the EU-only scenario would result in a 0.5% increase in the number of food insecure people in 77 countries, mainly in Africa and other Asian countries, by 0.4 % and 1%, respectively.

The “Middle scenario”

This scenario consists of expanding the above restrictions to regions outside the EU. Namely, EFTA countries, other European countries, Turkey, Ukraine, the Middle East, North Africa, and Africa would adopt the restrictions under this scenario. That is regions that either depend on exporting food and agricultural products to the EU or have a strong colonial past. For the rest of the regions, the model assumes the imposition of a 50% import restriction by the EU (**Beckman et al., 2020**).

Global production is estimated to present an overall decrease of 4%. The impact, of course, is not equally distributed among the various regions. EFTA, Middle East, and North African countries are estimated to observe a 15% decline in production. Both these regions are considered adopters under the Middle scenario. Regions non-adopters also, under this scenario, would face a reduction of food and agricultural production reduction, albeit smaller. The authors attribute this reduction to the reliance of non-adopter countries on trade with adopters.

As far as market prices are concerned, in adopter regions, prices are estimated to increase by at least 50%, while in specific commodities, mainly primary products such as crops, are expected to present a 3-digit increase. The authors attribute it to the two elements of the scenario, that is, the reduction of inputs for adopters and the trade restrictions for non-adopters. The decrease in the value of agricultural trade worldwide, if the middle scenario were to be implemented, is estimated to be 9%. GFI is expected to decrease in non-adopting regions, while the inverse is estimated in adopting regions due to the abovementioned price increase. Food expenditure per capita seems to increase by an average of \$159, mainly to adopter countries, while, according to the estimations of the model, food expenditure decreases in most non-adopting regions.

Regarding the impacts on food security, in the case of partial adoption of the restrictions, the authors predict a 2.2% increase in the food-insecure population due to the predicted increase in food prices.

Using a more elaborated version of the partial implementation scenario, based on game theory, **Beckman et al. (2022)** assume that regions that use smaller amounts of inputs than the ones imposed by the Green Deal (that is, 20% less fertilisers and -50% pesticides) will not face any impact on their production process but have to adopt the trade restrictions of the EU. This exercise resulted in more modest impacts on the global market impacts, namely global prices, output and trade.

The global scenario

Finally, the most “ambitious” scenario taken into account by the team in the ERS of the USDA was the global scenario, according to which the restrictions proposed by the EU Green Deal would be adopted globally.

Under this scenario, the researchers estimate a reduction of 11% in global agricultural production, although the impacts on individual global regions differ significantly. Thus, Ukraine, the former USSR and other European countries will face more considerable impacts, while Latin America (Mexico, Central America and South America, excluding Argentina and Brazil) will see a significant reduction. It is worth noting that the later regions under the middle scenario would not suffer any adverse effects. The Middle East and Africa are also estimated to suffer significant decreases but slightly less than the middle scenario.

As far as prices are concerned, there is an apparent expectation that prices will rise globally under this extreme scenario, with the “Former USSR and rest of Europe” region expected to have 3-digit increases and crops like rice, wheat and coarse grain facing the highest increases worldwide. Trade is also estimated to be reduced by 4% globally; however, according to the authors, the Middle East and Africa are estimated to have significant increases in their crop exports, while the picture is not that clear in the case of Latin America.

Moving to food expenditure and food security, it seems that expenses for food will significantly increase globally (\$450), while in Africa and the Middle East, the Former USSR and the rest of Europe, and Latin America, the increase estimated is even greater than the global average. Hence, the impact of global adoption of the restrictions proposed by the EU Green Deal is estimated as severe since there is an increase of 185 million people in the insecure population, which can be translated to a 3.9% increase in the prevalence of food insecurity worldwide. It also seems that Africa and Other Asia are the regions expected to be more affected, with an estimated increase of 80 and 72 million food insecure populations, respectively.

Regional distribution of impacts

Baquedano et al. (2022), elaborating further on the expected impact on 77 low and middle-income countries due to a hypothetical global adoption of the EU Green Deal restrictions, suggest that the expected improvement in global food security is going to be hampered by a 3.7% up to 2030. This negative outcome was estimated to be more pronounced in Sub-Saharan Africa, with a hindrance of 5.4% on average (10.5% in Southern Africa), 6.2% for Central America and

the Caribbean and an impressive 12.3% in Other Asia¹⁰. However, as the authors advise, the results should be treated with reservation since the proposal's specifics are unclear, not even for European farmers, much less how it could be implemented in the case of global adoption. Furthermore, the study mentioned does not account for investment in technology and innovation and their rate of acceptance by farmers, especially for the time scope of the study.

¹⁰ Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, Brunei Darussalam, Burma, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Macau, Malaysia, Maldives, Mongolia, Nepal, North Korea, Pakistan, Philippines, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Timor Leste, Vietnam

5. CONCLUSIONS

5.1 Policy coherence and sustainability issues in EU trade-related policies

The awareness of the problems caused by modern agrifood systems has led to efforts to transition to sustainable food systems. This transition is also necessitated by the COVID-19 crisis and the war in Ukraine, which have exposed vulnerabilities in agricultural and food systems.

The EU is crucial in promoting a transition to sustainable and resilient food systems, with its ambitious Green Deal and global role in agri-food markets. Trade agreements and bilateral cooperation offer opportunities to achieve sustainability standards with partner countries. The Green Deal strategy aims to facilitate the transition towards sustainable food systems, as outlined in the F2F and Biodiversity Strategies. In order to help resolve sustainability issues in trade policy, a diverse range of policy areas must be aligned. In addition, a series of policy contradictions, inconsistencies, and trade-offs must be overcome in seeking coherence between agricultural, environmental, and trade policies.

Scholars are cautious about the efficiency of the new EU trade policy strategy, which focuses on supporting sustainable value chains and setting global standards, promoting the green transition through trade. It includes policy initiatives to stimulate greening, such as liberalizing trade in sustainable goods and services and using sustainability standards throughout value chains. The strategy does not address the need for synergies between internal and external policies shaping trade, nor does it address the importance of existing initiatives like appointing a Chief Trade Enforcement Officer and establishing a Single Entry Point.

The Green Deal's measures may severely impact production structures, reducing production, increasing costs, and impacting exports and global food security. However, the environmental ambition of the Green Deal cannot be achieved alone, as climate change and biodiversity loss are global.

Concerns have arisen that the F2F Strategy may lead to off-shoring food and agricultural production overseas, potentially undermining policy objectives. Also, the F2F adjustment costs are distributed asymmetrically between consumers and farmers and among the farmers themselves; less competitive farms would completely give up production, and more competitive farms survive to collect the higher profits from higher farm prices while exiting farms would realize a loss. In contrast to farmers, agricultural processing industries face a decrease in value-added by the F2F strategy. F2F causes changes in food security, poverty or biodiversity in non-EU countries that can be considered relevant to European society. The most substantial leakage effects can be observed within animal production.

The F2F Strategy does not yet correspond to a consistent agricultural policy strategy, as individual measures are specific production restrictions that do not provide a consistent framework for implementing the Green Deal's goals in agriculture. The literature has identified several key issues that the F2F Strategy has to address: (i) it is ineffective in reducing climate change, particularly regarding GHG emissions; (ii) it should include the LULUCF-Sector (Land-Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry), which accounts for 48% of the compensation for the F2F-induced reduction of GHG emissions in agriculture; (iii) the strategy's actions should be goal-oriented, with political restrictions targeting ecosystem services provided by agriculture; (iv) the strategy must ensure a socially just distribution of adjustment costs; (v) finally, the Green Deal goals require smart and innovative governance mechanisms that combine market flexibility and planning security with regulatory policy interventions.

Legal basis, political commitment and demand from civil society exist for the EU trade relations in general, and its bilateral trade agreements in particular, to support the achievement of the SDGs internally and deliver for sustainability globally. However, recent studies show that the EU generally outsources economic, social and environmental impacts abroad, notably through trade. There is, therefore, an urgent need to make EU trade and its impacts on global value chains more sustainable. Improving EU FTAs regarding the scope of their sustainability commitments and monitoring and enforcement mechanisms is a crucial part of that objective as they encompass a large share of EU trade.

We have examined EU trade agreements regarding including sustainability-related policies within agricultural trade. This examination concerns all the agreements and political initiatives that make up the 'core' trade policy of the EU, i.e., the 44 "Agreements in place" involving 77 countries/regions and the 5 "Agreements being adopted or ratified" involving 25 countries/ regions. A central part of our study involved identifying provisions in the trade agreements under consideration, focusing specifically on the agricultural trade/sector concerning sustainability aspects.

A few trade agreements consider agriculture's environmental impact in their provisions. These agreements include issues such as a) the impact on soil and water quality, b) soil erosion and pollution by agricultural chemicals, c) the management of impacts through the use of antibiotics and decontaminants, d) conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity, and e) genetically modified organisms. It should also be noted that the trade agreements include climate/climate change-related provisions in several cases. However, there is no mention of the agricultural trade or the sector.

5.2 Policy proposals

5.2.1 EU Organic farming certification scheme

The issue raised by the CS partners but also proposed as prominent by the relevant literature is the decision of the EU not to proceed to the solution of equivalence but rather to impose the procedure of individual recognition of control and auditing organisations as almost the only solution for countries wishing to export their organic produce to any EU country. Formal recognition and encouragement of regional organic standards, such as the East African Organic Products Standard (EAOPS), the Pacific Organic Standard (POS), the Central American initiative, the Asia Regional Organic Standard (AROS), the African Regional Standard (ARS), and lastly, the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) Standard for Organic Agriculture (ASOA) would be a crucial step towards that direction.

On the other hand, countries having a vested interest in the promotion of their organic exports, for example, countries where organic farming is increasing rapidly and can be an essential factor in alleviating poverty and setting the basis of sustainable growth of their agriculture, could increase their efforts to cooperate effectively among them and the private sector, involving all relevant stakeholders in order to promote the idea of regional standards, better adapted to the local circumstances, adopting effectively local practices.

Adopting group certification could solve the second issue raised, i.e., the certification costs. Promoting such efforts, especially those under participatory certification schemes, could also contribute to fulfilling the need for adaptation to local circumstances. According to **Willer et al. (2023)**, there are 323 Participatory Guarantee Schemes in 76 countries, with more than 1.4 million farmers involved (more than 1.3 million certified) managing 887.744 hectares of land. Many of these initiatives are encountered in Africa, Asia and Latin America, and the number of initiatives involving farmers and areas covered is increasing yearly.

5.2.2 Harmonised Food safety regulations for EU imports

An increase in resources dedicated to research in order to find alternative methods to pesticides would contribute to a reduction of the need for their use. An essential part of the funds targets such goals within the EU research framework. An increased effort towards research focusing on phytosanitary issues prevalent in developing countries could significantly contribute to this direction.

Taking stock of local practices, knowledge, and experience systematically, utilising current technologies, and creating knowledge bases accessible to farmers and practitioners in developing countries would be other vital steps.

5.2.3 Agricultural Extension and Training

The literature and all partners' responses stressed the importance of reinforcing and reforming the Agricultural Extension service towards an integrated knowledge management system with access to research results, information and all available IT (Information Technology) methods and equipment.

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Appendix I: TARIFF QUOTAS

A **tariff quota** allows for the duty-free or reduced-rate importation of a certain amount of a commodity, while any quantities imported in excess of the quota are subject to a higher duty rate. Tariff quotas approved on the basis of Article 31 of the Treaty of the Functioning of the EU constitute an exception to the normal state of affairs since they permit, during the period of validity of the measure and for a limited quantity, the total (total suspension) or partial waiver (partial suspension) of the normal duties applicable to imported goods (antidumping duties are not affected by these suspensions).

In the framework of several agreements that the EU has concluded with third countries/territories and autonomous preferential arrangements for some beneficiary countries/territories, **tariff concessions** are provided for a predetermined volume of goods. These tariff concessions are called 'preferential tariff quotas'. Within these **preferential tariff quotas**, a predetermined volume of goods originating in a specified country/territory can benefit at import into the Union from a more favourable duty rate than the normal third countries/territories duty mentioned in the combined nomenclature.

Entitlement to benefit from preferential tariff quotas is subject to the presentation of the necessary evidence of origin.

Nevertheless, products originating in Western Sahara subject to controls by customs authorities of the Kingdom of Morocco shall benefit from the same trade preferences as those granted by the European Union to products covered by the Association Agreement.

Autonomous tariff quotas

As stated already for suspensions, for some economic sectors, it is necessary to stimulate competition by low tariffs, as we find in numerous industrial sectors.

Their role is to stimulate the economic activity of Union industries, improve competitive capacity, create employment, modernise structures, etc.

They are normally granted to raw materials, semi-finished goods or components not available in the EU (suspensions) or which are available but in insufficient quantities (tariff quotas), **but no tariff quotas are granted for finished products.**

A request to open an autonomous tariff quota may be presented as such or result from the examination of a suspension request. In this connection, account will be taken, where appropriate, of consequential damage to any new production and manufacturing capacity, which could be made available in the Union or a third country/territory with preferential tariff arrangements.

When identical, equivalent or substitute products are manufactured in sufficient quantities within the EU or by producers in a third country/territory with preferential tariff arrangements, the granting of a quota is normally excluded. The same applies where the measure could result in a distortion of competition regarding the final products.

Council Regulation 2021/2283 opening and providing for the management of autonomous tariff quotas of the Union for certain agricultural and industrial products (Official Journal L 458 of 22.12.2021, p.33) establishes the list of goods subject to these measures. It is regularly amended (in January and July each year) to consider new requests presented by the Member States.

Information on the products currently examined by the Commission with the aid of the Economic Tariff Question Group.

More information and forms concerning autonomous tariff suspensions and quotas can be found in the Commission Communication (Official Journal C 363 of 13.12.2011, p.6).

Council Regulation (EU) 2020/1706 of 13 November 2020 opening and providing for the management of autonomous Union tariff quotas for certain fishery products for the period 2021-2023 (Official Journal L 385, 13.11.2020, p. 3), establishes the list of fishery products subject to autonomous tariff quotas.

Management

The Commission's Directorate-General manages most tariff quotas and is responsible for the Taxation and Customs Union on a 'first-come, first-served' basis, irrespective of where the goods are imported into the EU. The legal provisions governing the management of these tariff quotas are contained in Articles 49 to 54 of the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2015/2447 of 24 November 2015, which lays down detailed rules for implementing certain provisions of the UCC.

Information about the current balances of those tariff quotas, managed on a first-come, first-served basis, is available [on-line](#).

Agricultural

Some tariff quotas are managed by the Commission's Directorate-General, responsible for Agriculture and Rural Development through a system of import licenses. Various Council and Commission Regulations contain specific provisions for managing these tariff quotas.

Appendix II: EU Trade Agreements: Provisions on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects

Country/ies	Document	Article	Title	Text
Agreements in place				
Albania	Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Albania, of the other part	Article 95	Agriculture and the agro-industrial sector	Cooperation between the Parties shall focus on priority areas related to the Community acquis in the field of agriculture. Cooperation shall notably aim at modernising and restructuring the Albanian agriculture and agro-industrial sector, and at supporting the gradual approximation of Albanian legislation and practices to the Community rules and standards.
Algeria	Euro-Mediterranean association agreement between the European Community and its Members States, of the one part, and the People's Democratic Republic of Algeria, of the other part	Article 58	Agriculture and fisheries	Cooperation shall be aimed at the modernisation and restructuring, where necessary, of the agriculture, forestry and fisheries sectors. It shall in particular be aimed at: support for policies geared to developing and diversifying production; food security; integrated rural development, including improvement of basic services and development of ancillary economic activities; promoting environmentally-friendly forms of agriculture and fisheries; the evaluation and rational management of natural resources; establishing closer relations, on a voluntary basis, between enterprises, groupings and professional organisations representing the agricultural, fisheries and agri-business sectors; technical assistance and training; harmonising phytosanitary and veterinary standards and checks; cooperation between rural areas, exchange of experience and know-how on rural development; support for privatization; the evaluation and rational management of fish stocks; support for research programmes.
Andorra	Agreement in the form of an exchange of letters between the European Economic Community and the Principality of Andorra	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Antigua and	Economic Partnership	Article 37	Agriculture and	1. The Parties agree that the fundamental objective of this Agreement is

Barbuda, Bahamas, Barbados, Belize, Dominica, Dominican Republic, Grenada, Guyana, Jamaica, St Kitts and Nevis, St Lucia, St Vincent and the Grenadines, Suriname, Trinidad and Tobago (CARIFORUM States)	Agreement between the CARIFORUM States, of the one part, and the European Community and its Member States, of the other part		fisheries - Objectives	<p>the sustainable development and the eradication of poverty in CARIFORUM States, and the smooth and gradual integration of these economies into the global economy. In the agricultural and fisheries sectors, this Agreement should contribute to increasing the competitiveness of production, processing and trade in agricultural and fishery products in both traditional and non-traditional sectors, between the Parties, consistent with the sustainable management of natural resources.</p> <p>4. The Parties recognise that ensuring food security and enhancing livelihoods of rural and fishing communities are critical elements of the eradication of poverty, and the pursuit of sustainable development. They consequently recognise the need to avoid major disruption of markets for agricultural, food and fish products in CARIFORUM States.</p>
-//-	-//-	Article 43	Agriculture and fisheries - Cooperation	<p>1. The Parties acknowledge the importance of the agricultural, food and fisheries sectors to the economies of CARIFORUM States and of cooperating to promote the transformation of these sectors, with the aim of increasing their competitiveness, developing their capacity to access high quality markets and in view of their potential contribution to the sustainable development of the CARIFORUM States. They recognise the need to facilitate the adjustment of the agricultural, food and fisheries sectors and the rural economy, to the progressive changes brought about by this Agreement, while paying particular attention to small scale operations.</p> <p>2. Subject to the provisions of Article 7, the Parties agree to cooperate, including by facilitating support, in the following areas:</p> <p>(c) Compliance with and adoption of quality standards relating to food production and marketing, including standards relating to environmentally and socially sound agricultural practices and organic and non-genetically modified foods;</p>
Armenia	Partnership and cooperation agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of	Article 53	Agriculture and the agro-industrial sector	The purpose of cooperation in this area shall be the pursuance of agrarian reform, the modernisation, privatisation and restructuring of agriculture, the agro-industrial and service sectors in the Republic of Armenia, development of domestic and foreign markets for Armenian products, in conditions that ensure the protection of the environment, taking into account the necessity to improve security of food supply as

	Armenia, of the other part			well as the development of agri-business, the processing and distribution of agricultural products. The Parties shall also aim at the gradual approximation of Armenian standards to Community technical regulations concerning industrial and agricultural food products including sanitary and phytosanitary standards.
Azerbaijan	Partnership and cooperation agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Azerbaijan, of the other part	Article 54	Agriculture and the agro-industrial sector	The purpose of cooperation in this area shall be the pursuance of agrarian reform, the modernisation, privatisation and restructuring of agriculture, the agro-industrial and service sectors in the Republic of Azerbaijan, development of domestic and foreign markets for Azerbaijani products, in conditions that ensure the protection of the environment, taking into account the necessity to improve security of food supply as well as the development of agribusiness, the processing and distribution of agricultural products. The Parties shall also aim at the gradual approximation of Azerbaijani standards to Community technical regulations concerning industrial and agricultural food products including sanitary and phytosanitary standards.
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and Bosnia and Herzegovina, of the other part	Article 95	Agriculture, and the agro-industrial sector	Cooperation between the Parties shall focus on priority areas related to the Community acquis in the field of agriculture and veterinary and phytosanitary domains. Cooperation shall notably aim at modernising and restructuring the agriculture and agro-industrial sector in Bosnia and Herzegovina, in particular to reach veterinary and phytosanitary Community requirements and at supporting the progressive approximation of the legislation and practices of Bosnia and Herzegovina to the Community rules and standards.
Botswana, Eswatini, Lesotho, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa (SADC)	Economic Partnership Agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and the SADC EPA States, of the other part	Article 68	Cooperation on agriculture	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Parties underline the importance of the agricultural sector to the SADC EPA States for food security, generating rural employment, increasing incomes of farm households, creating an inclusive rural economy, and as a basis for wider industrialisation and sustainable development, as well as to contribute to the objectives of this Agreement. 2. The use of export subsidies on agricultural goods in the trade between the Parties shall not be allowed from the date of entry into force of this Agreement. 3. An agricultural partnership is established between the EU and the

				SADC EPA States to facilitate an exchange of views between the Parties on agriculture, inter alia, food security, development, regional value chains and integration. The coverage of issues and operational rules for the agricultural partnership shall be established by common agreement of the Parties acting within the Committee referred to in Article 103.
Cameroon	Economic Partnership Agreement between the European Community and its Member States, of the one part, and the Central Africa Party, of the other part	ANNEX I	2. Agriculture and food safety at regional level	2.1. Support for improving productivity (seed programme, research and dissemination); 2.2. Development of agro-industries; 2.3. Improvement in trade in agricultural products; 2.4. Support for the implementation of a regional common agricultural policy
Canada	Comprehensive Economic and Trade Agreement (CETA) between Canada, of the one part, and the European Union and its Member States, of the other part	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Chile	Agreement establishing an association between the European Community and its Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Chile, of the other part	Article 24	Cooperation on agriculture and rural sectors and sanitary and phytosanitary measures	<p>1. Cooperation in this area is designed to support and stimulate agricultural policy measures in order to promote and consolidate the Parties' efforts towards a sustainable agriculture and agricultural and rural development.</p> <p>2. The cooperation shall focus on capacity-building, infrastructure and technology transfer, addressing matters such as: (a) specific projects aimed at supporting sanitary, phytosanitary, environmental and food quality measures, taking into account the legislation in force for both Parties, in compliance with WTO rules and other competent international organisations; (b) diversification and restructuring of agricultural sectors; (c) the mutual exchange of information, including that concerning the development of the Parties' agricultural policies; (d) technical assistance for the improvement of productivity and the exchange of alternative crop technologies; (e) scientific and technological experiments; (f) measures aimed at enhancing the quality of agricultural products and supporting trade promotion activities; (g) technical assistance for the strengthening of sanitary and phytosanitary</p>

				control systems, with a view to supporting as far as possible the promotion of equivalence and mutual recognition agreements.
Colombia, Ecuador, Peru	Trade Agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and Colombia, Ecuador and Peru, of the other part	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Comoros, Madagascar, Mauritius, Seychelles, Zimbabwe (ESA)	Interim Agreement establishing a framework for an Economic Partnership Agreement between the Eastern and Southern Africa States, on the one part, and the European Community and its Member States, on the other part	ANNEX IV	DEVELOPMENT MATRIX (a) Agriculture and Livestock	Promote sustainable agriculture, improve production, productivity and diversification, develop agro-industry, trade, and ensure food security Activities could be: (i) Development of harmonised regional policies, legal and regulatory frameworks, Standards and Quality Assurance and certification instruments accredited to international standards and capacity building on sustainable production systems. (ii) Construct and improve irrigation facilities and infrastructure, rural infrastructure linking production areas to markets, cold storage chains and related infrastructure. (iii) Promotion of Agricultural/Livestock R&D and its implementation; gender mainstreaming in access to production factors; strengthening of the value chain and technology transfer. (iv) Development of special vehicle insurance schemes and instruments for access to finance. (v) Establish and strengthen institutions to promote modalities of disease handling, implement national and trans-boundary disease control programme and establishment of national and regional early warning systems and centres of excellence for agricultural workers.
Costa Rica, El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, Nicaragua (Central America)	Agreement establishing an Association between the European Union and its Member States, on the one hand, and Central America on the other	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Côte d'Ivoire	Stepping stone Economic Partnership Agreement between Côte d'Ivoire, of the one part, and the European Community and its Member	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects

	States, of the other part			
Egypt	Euro-Mediterranean agreement establishing an association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Arab Republic of Egypt, of the other part	Article 50	Agriculture and fisheries	Cooperation shall be aimed at: (a) the modernisation and restructuring of agriculture and fisheries, including: the modernisation of infrastructures and of equipment; the development of packaging, storage and marketing techniques; the improvement of private distribution channels; (b) the diversification of production and of external outlets, inter alia, through the encouragement of joint ventures in the agri-business sector; (c) the promotion of cooperation in veterinary and phytosanitary matters and in growing techniques, with the objective of facilitating trade between the Parties. In this regard, the Parties shall exchange information.
Faroe Islands	Agreement between the European Community, of the one part, and the Government of Denmark and the Home Government of the Faroe Islands, of the other part	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Fiji, Papua New Guinea, Samoa, Solomon Islands (Pacific)	Interim Partnership Agreement between the European Community, of the one part, and the Pacific States, of the other part	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Georgia	Association agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and Georgia, of the other part	Article 333	Agriculture and rural development	Cooperation between the Parties in the field of agriculture and rural development shall cover, inter alia, the following areas: (a) facilitating the mutual understanding of agricultural and rural development policies; (b) enhancing the administrative capacities at central and local level to plan, evaluate, implement and enforce policies in accordance with EU regulations and best practices; (c) promoting the modernisation and the sustainability of the agricultural production; (d) sharing knowledge and best practices of rural development policies to promote economic well-being for rural communities; (e) improving the competitiveness of the agricultural sector and the efficiency and transparency for all stakeholders in the markets; (f) promoting quality policies and their control mechanisms, including geographical indications and organic

				farming; (g) wine production and agro tourism; (h) disseminating knowledge and promoting extension services to agricultural producers, and (i) striving for the harmonisation of issues dealt within the framework of international organisations of which both Parties are members.
Ghana	Stepping stone Economic Partnership Agreement between Ghana, of the one part, and the European Community and its Member States, of the other part	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway	Agreement of the European Economic Area, Main Part	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Iraq	Partnership and cooperation agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Iraq, of the other part	Article 90	Cooperation on agriculture, forestry and rural development	The objective is to promote cooperation in the agriculture, forestry and rural development sectors with a view to promoting diversification, environmentally sound practices, sustainable economic and social development and food security. To this end the Parties will examine: (a) capacity building and training to public institutions; (b) measures aimed at enhancing the quality of agricultural products, capacity building measures for producers associations and supporting trade promotion activities; (c) environmental health, animal and plant health measures and other related aspects, taking account of the legislation in force for both parties, in compliance with WTO and multilateral environmental agreement rules; (d) measures relating to sustainable economic and social development of rural territories, including environmentally sound practices, forestry, research, transfer of know-how, access to land, water management and irrigation, sustainable rural development and food security; (e) measures relating to preservation of agricultural traditional

				knowledge that give their populations their specific identities, including cooperation on geographical indications, exchanges of experiences at local level and development of cooperation networks; (f) modernisation of agricultural sector including farming practices and diversification of agricultural production.
Israel	Euro-Mediterranean agreement establishing an association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the State of Israel, of the other part	Article 46	Agriculture	The Parties shall focus cooperation in particular on: support for policies implemented by them to diversify production; promotion of environment-friendly agriculture; closer relations between businesses, groups and organisations representing trades and professions in Israel and in the Community on a voluntary basis; technical assistance and training; harmonisation of phytosanitary and veterinary standards; integrated rural development, including improvement in basic services and development of associated economic activities; cooperation among rural regions, exchange of experience and know-how concerning rural development.
Japan	Agreement between the European Union and Japan for an Economic Partnership	Article 19.1	COOPERATION IN THE FIELD OF AGRICULTURE ARTICLE - Objectives	The Parties recognise that promoting trade in agricultural products and foods between them is in their mutual interest, and aim at promoting cooperation on sustainable agriculture, including rural development and the exchange of technical information and best practices for providing safe and high quality foods for consumers in the European Union and Japan.
-//-	-//-	Article 19.2	COOPERATION IN THE FIELD OF AGRICULTURE ARTICLE - Scope	1. The Parties shall cooperate in the areas referred to in Article 19.1 in accordance with their respective laws and regulations. The Parties shall encourage and facilitate cooperation among relevant groups, entities, competent authorities and other organisations of the Parties. 2. The scope of cooperation referred to in paragraph 1 shall cover: (a) the promotion of trade in agricultural products and foods, including a dialogue on the relevant regulation; (b) cooperation with a view to improving farm management, productivity and competitiveness, including the exchange of best practices regarding sustainable agriculture, as well as the use of technology and innovation; (c) cooperation on production and technology in agriculture and foods;
Jordan	Euro-Mediterranean agreement establishing an	Article 71	Agriculture	The Parties shall focus cooperation in particular on: support for policies implemented by them to diversify production; promotion of

	association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, of the other part			environment-friendly agriculture; closer relations between businesses, groups and organisations representing trades and professions in Jordan and in the Community on a voluntary basis; technical assistance and training; harmonisation of phytosanitary and veterinary standards; integrated rural development, including improvement in basic services and development of associated economic activities; cooperation among rural regions, exchange of experience and know-how concerning rural development.
Kazakhstan	Enhanced Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Kazakhstan, of the other part	Article 229	Cooperation in the area of agriculture and rural development	Cooperation shall cover, among others, the following areas: (a) facilitating the mutual understanding of agricultural and rural development policies; (b) exchanging best practices in the planning, evaluation and implementation of agricultural and rural development policies; (c) sharing knowledge and best practices with regard to rural development policies to promote social and economic well-being for rural inhabitants; (d) promoting the modernisation and the sustainability of agricultural production; (e) improving the competitiveness of the agricultural sector and the efficiency and transparency of the markets; (f) exchanging experience in geographical indications for agricultural products and foodstuffs, in quality policies and their control mechanisms, in ensuring food safety and in the development of the production of organic agricultural products; (g) disseminating knowledge and promoting extension services to agricultural producers; (h) promoting cooperation in agro-industrial investments projects, in particular in the development of the livestock and crop sectors; (i) exchanging experience in policies related to sustainable development of agribusiness and the processing and distribution of agricultural products.
Kosovo	Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community, of the one part, and Kosovo, of the other part	Article 102	Agriculture and the agro-industrial sector	Cooperation between the Parties shall be developed in all priority areas related to the EU acquis in the field of agriculture, as well as on quality schemes for agricultural products and foodstuffs, food safety, veterinary and phytosanitary domains. Cooperation shall notably aim at modernising and restructuring the agriculture and agro-industrial sector in Kosovo, particular to reach EU sanitary requirements, to improve water management and rural development as well as to develop the related aspects of the forestry sector in Kosovo and at supporting the gradual approximation of Kosovo legislation and practices to the EU

				acquis.
Lebanon	Euro-Mediterranean agreement establishing an association between the European Community and its Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Lebanon, of the other part	Article 51	Agriculture and fisheries	The aims of cooperation shall be: (a) to support policies aiming to diversify production; (b) to reduce food dependency; (c) to promote a form of agriculture which pays due regard to the environment; (d) to establish closer relations between enterprises, groupings and professional organisations of the two Parties; (e) to provide assistance and technical training; support for agronomic research, advisory services, agricultural education and technical training of staff in the agricultural sector; (f) to harmonise phytosanitary and veterinary standards; (g) to support integrated rural development, including improvement of basic services and development of ancillary economic activities, particularly in the regions affected by the eradication of illicit crops; (h) cooperation between rural areas, exchange of experience and know-how on rural development; (i) development of sea fishing and aquaculture; (j) development of packaging, storage and marketing techniques; and the improvement of distribution channels; (k) to develop agricultural water resources; (l) to develop the forestry sector, especially in the fields of reforestation, forest fire prevention, forest pasture and combating desertification; (m) to develop agricultural mechanisation and promotion of agricultural service cooperatives; (n) to strengthen the agricultural credit system.
Mexico	Economic Partnership, Political Coordination and Cooperation Agreement between the European Community and its Member States of the one part, and the United Mexican States, of the other part	Article 21	Cooperation in agriculture and the rural sector	1. The Parties undertake to promote development and cooperation in the agricultural, agroindustrial and rural sectors. 2. To this end they shall examine , inter alia, the following: (a) measures to harmonize health, plant-health and environmental standards and rules, with a view to facilitating trade, taking account of the legislation in force for both Parties and in conformity with the rules of the WTO, in addition to the terms of Article 5; (b) the potential for exchanging information and setting up projects and activities, with that aim in mind, notably in the fields of information, scientific and technical research and the development of human resources.
Moldova	Association agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their	Article 68	Agriculture and rural development	Cooperation between the Parties in the field of agriculture and rural development shall cover, inter alia, the following areas: (a) facilitating the mutual understanding of agricultural and rural development policies; (b) enhancing the administrative capacities at central and local level in

	Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Moldova, of the other part			the planning, evaluation and implementation of policies in accordance with EU regulations and best practices; (c) promoting the modernisation and the sustainability of agricultural production; (d) sharing knowledge and best practices of rural development policies to promote economic well-being for rural communities; (e) improving the competitiveness of the agricultural sector and the efficiency and transparency of the markets; (f) promoting quality policies and their control mechanisms, in particular geographical indications and organic farming; (g) disseminating knowledge and promoting extension services to agricultural producers; and (h) enhancing the harmonisation of issues dealt within the framework of international organisations of which the Parties are members.
Montenegro	Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Montenegro, of the other part	Article 97	Agriculture, and the agro-industrial sector	Cooperation between the Parties shall be developed in all priority areas related to the Community acquis in the field of agriculture, as well as veterinary and phytosanitary domains. Cooperation shall notably aim at modernising and restructuring the agriculture and agro-industrial sector, in particular to reach community sanitary requirements, to improve water management and rural development as well as to develop the forestry sector in Montenegro and at supporting the gradual approximation of Montenegrin legislation and practices to the Community rules and standards.
Morocco	Euro-Mediterranean agreement establishing an association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Kingdom of Morocco, of the other part		Agriculture and fisheries	The aim of cooperation shall be to: (a) modernise and restructure agriculture and fisheries through methods including the modernisation of infrastructure and equipment, the development of packaging and storage techniques and the improvement of private distribution and marketing chains; (b) diversify output and external markets; (c) achieve cooperation in health, plant health and growing techniques.
North Macedonia	Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the former Yugoslav Republic of	Article 100	Agriculture, and the agro-industrial sector	Cooperation in this field shall have as its aim the modernization and restructuring of agriculture and the agro-industrial sector, water management, rural development, the gradual harmonisation of veterinary and phytosanitary legislation with Community standards and the development of fishery and forestry sectors in the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia.

	Macedonia, of the other part			
Palestinian Authority of the West Bank and the Gaza Strip	Council Decision of 2 June 1997 concerning the conclusion of the Euro-Mediterranean Interim Association Agreement on trade and cooperation between the European Community, of the one part, and the Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO) for the benefit of the Palestinian Authority of the West Bank and the Gaza Strip	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
San Marino	Agreement on Cooperation and Customs Union between the European Economic Community and the Republic of San Marino	Article 6	-	In trade in agricultural products between the Community and San Marino, the Republic of San Marino undertakes to adopt Community veterinary, plant health and quality regulations where necessary for the proper functioning of the Agreement.
Serbia	Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Communities and their Member States of the one part, and the Republic of Serbia, of the other part	Article 97	Agriculture, and the agro-industrial sector	Cooperation between the Parties shall be developed in all priority areas related to the Community acquis in the field of agriculture, as well as veterinary and phytosanitary domains. Cooperation shall notably aim at modernising and restructuring the agriculture and agro-industrial sector, in particular to reach community sanitary requirements, to improve water management and rural development as well as to develop the forestry sector in Serbia and at supporting the gradual approximation of Serbian legislation and practices to the Community rules and standards.
Singapore	FREE TRADE AGREEMENT BETWEEN THE EUROPEAN UNION AND THE REPUBLIC OF SINGAPORE	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
South Korea	Free Trade Agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects

	Korea, of the other part			
Switzerland	Agreement between the European Economic Community and the Swiss Confederation	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Tunisia	Euro-Mediterranean agreement establishing an association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Tunisia, of the other part	Article 54	Agriculture and fisheries	The aim of cooperation shall be to: (a) modernise and restructure agriculture and fisheries through methods including the modernisation of infrastructure and equipment, the development of packaging and storage techniques and the improvement of private distribution and marketing chains; (b) diversify output and external markets; (c) achieve cooperation in health, plant health and growing techniques.
Turkey	Decision No 1 /95 of the EC-Turkey association council on implementing the final phase of the Customs Union	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Ukraine	Association agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and Ukraine, of the other part	Article 404	Agriculture and rural development	Cooperation between the Parties in the field of agriculture and rural development shall cover, inter alia, the following areas: (a) facilitating mutual understanding of agricultural and rural development policies; (b) enhancing administrative capacities at central and local levels for the planning, evaluation and implementation of policies; (c) promoting modern and sustainable agricultural production, respectful of the environment and of animal welfare, including extension of the use of organic production methods and the use of biotechnologies, inter alia through the implementation of best practices in those fields; (d) sharing knowledge and best practices of rural development policies to promote economic well-being for rural communities; (e) improving the competitiveness of the agricultural sector and the efficiency and transparency of the markets as well as conditions for investment; (f) disseminating knowledge through training and information events; (g) favouring innovation through research and promoting extension services to agricultural producers; (h) enhancing harmonisation of issues addressed within the framework of international organisations; (i) exchanging best practices on support mechanisms for agricultural

				policies and rural areas; (j) promoting the policy of quality of agricultural products in the areas of product standards, production requirements and quality schemes.
United Kingdom	Trade and Cooperation Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community, of the one part, and the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, of the other part	Article 69	SANITARY AND PHYTOSANITARY MEASURES - Objectives	(e) enhance cooperation between the Parties in the fight against antimicrobial resistance, promotion of sustainable food systems, protection of animal welfare, and on electronic certification.
Viet Nam	Free Trade Agreement between the European Union and the Socialist Republic of Viet Nam	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Agreements being adopted or ratified				
Argentina, Brazil, Paraguay, Uruguay (Mercosur)	Trade part of the EU-Mercosur Association Agreement	CHAPTER DIALOGUES Article 3	Animal welfare	Recognizing that animals are sentient beings, the Parties will conduct a dialogue that will cover, inter alia: 1. Specific topics on animal welfare that may affect mutual trade; 2. Exchange of information, expertise and experiences in the field of animal welfare to improve their respective approaches on regulatory standards related to breeding, holding, handling, transportation and slaughter of animals to their mutual benefits. 3. Strengthen the research collaboration. 4. Collaboration in international fora with the aim to promote the further development of international standards on animal welfare by the World Organization for Animal Health (OIE) and best animal welfare practices and their implementation.
-//-	-//-	CHAPTER DIALOGUES Article 4	Agricultural biotechnology	This dialogue will cover, inter alia: 1. To exchange information on policies, legislation, guidelines, good practices, and projects of agricultural biotechnology products. 2. To discuss specific topics on biotechnology that may affect mutual trade, including cooperation on

				GMO testing. 3. To exchange information on topics related to asynchronous authorisations of genetically modified organisms in order to minimize possible impact on trade. 4. To exchange information on the economic and trade outlook of authorisations of genetically modified products; 5. To exchange information on cases of low level presence of GMOs non-authorised by the importing Party, but authorised by the exporting Party.
-//-	-//-	CHAPTER DIALOGUES Article 5	Combating antimicrobial resistance	This dialogue will cover, inter alia: 1. The collaboration to follow up existing and future guidelines, standards, recommendations and actions developed in relevant international organisations, initiatives and national plans aiming to promote the prudent and responsible use of antibiotics and relating to animal production and veterinary practices. 2. The collaboration in the implementation of the recommendations of OIE, WHO and Codex, in particular CAC-RCP61/2005. 3. The exchange of information on good farming practices. 4. The promotion of research, innovation and development. 5. The promotion of multidisciplinary approaches to combat antimicrobial resistance, including the One Health approach of WHO, OIE and Codex Alimentarius.
-//-	-//-	CHAPTER DIALOGUES Article 6	Scientific matters related to food safety, animal and plant health	1. The Parties should foster the cooperation between their respective official scientific bodies responsible for food safety, animal and plant health science. This cooperation will aim to deepen the scientific information available to the Parties in order to support their respective approaches on regulatory standards that may affect mutual trade.
Benin, Burkina Faso, Cabo Verde, Gambia, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Togo (West Africa)	Economic partnership agreement between the West African States, the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) and the West African Economic and Monetary Union (UEMOA), of the one part, and the European Union and its Member States, of the other part	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects

Burundi, Kenya, Rwanda, Tanzania, Uganda (EAC)	Economic Partnership Agreement between the East African Community Partner States, of the one part, and the European Union and its Member States of the other part	Article 58	AGRICULTURE - Objectives	<p>1. The Parties agree that the fundamental objective of this Part is sustainable agricultural development which includes but is not limited to food and livelihoods security, rural development and poverty reduction in the EAC Partner States.</p> <p>2. The objectives of this Part are to: (a) foster cooperation between the Parties with a view to creating wealth and improving the quality of life of those engaged in agricultural activities through increased production, productivity and market share. (b) improve food and nutrition security in the EAC Partner States by promoting value addition, increasing output, quality, safety, market integration, trade, availability and accessibility. (c) contribute to provision of gainful employment throughout the value chain of modernised agricultural sector. (d) develop modern and competitive agro-based industries. (e) promote sustainable use and management of natural and cultural resources by developing environmentally friendly and sustainable technologies that improve the agricultural productivity. (f) contribute to competitiveness by promoting value addition throughout the supply chains to access markets. (g) improve producers' revenue by developing the marketing of value added agricultural products in the marketplace (h) facilitate the adjustment of the agricultural sector and the rural economy, to cope with global economic changes (i) mobilize and increase the economic performance of small scale farmers through capacity building of farmers' organisations. (j) improve trade and market facilitation for agricultural commodities in order to increase foreign exchange earnings. (k) improve infrastructure within EAC Partner States for enhancing production, productivity, marketing and distribution of agricultural inputs and products, with particular attention to storage, grading, handling, packing and transport.</p>
-//-	-//-	Article 59	AGRICULTURE - General Principles	<p>1. The Parties recognise the importance of agriculture in EAC Partner States economies, as the main source of livelihood for the majority of the EAC Partner States' population, as the primary factor to ensure food and nutrition security, potential sector for high growth and added value and a source of export earnings.</p> <p>2. In view of the multi-functional role agriculture plays in the economy of the EAC Partner States, the Parties agree to use a comprehensive approach to agriculture as a basis for sustainable development.</p>

				<p>3. The Parties agree to cooperate in promoting the sustainable growth of the agriculture sector, taking into account its multiple facets and the diversity of the economic, social, environmental characteristics and development strategies of the EAC Partner States.</p> <p>4. The Parties recognize that deeper integration of the agricultural sector across the EAC Partner States will contribute to the expansion of inter-regional markets, and increase the scope for investment and private sector development.</p> <p>5. The Parties recognize the importance of supporting agricultural production, promotion of value addition, agricultural trade and market development initiatives through appropriate instruments and provision of appropriate regulatory framework to respond to changing market conditions. In this respect, the Parties resolve to work together to attract necessary investment into the EAC Partner States.</p> <p>6. The Parties agree that agricultural priorities considered in this Part shall be clearly linked to the regional overarching policy framework for food and nutrition security and poverty reduction to ensure consistency and guidance of the regional development agenda.</p>
-//-	-//-	Article 63	AGRICULTURE - Sustainable Agricultural Development	The Parties shall cooperate in achieving sustainable agricultural development with special focus on supporting vulnerable rural population in the EAC Partner States in light of the changing world production and trade patterns as well as consumer tastes and preference.
-//-	-//-	Article 64	AGRICULTURE - Food and Nutrition Security	<p>1. The Parties agree that the provisions of this Agreement shall enable the EAC Partner States implement effective measures to achieve food and nutrition security and sustainable agricultural development, and to develop commercial agricultural markets in the region to ensure food and nutrition security.</p> <p>2. The Parties shall ensure that actions taken under this Part aim at enhancing food and nutrition security, and avoiding adoption of measures that could endanger achievement of food and nutrition security at the household, national and regional levels.</p>
-//-	-//-	Article 65	AGRICULTURE - Value Chain	The Parties agree to have a regional strategy for enhancing supply capacities in agriculture, identifying high value agricultural sub-sectors for which the region has competitive advantage and capitalise on

			Management	investments that can facilitate the shift from comparative to competitive advantages.
-//-	-//-	Article 66	AGRICULTURE - Early Warning Systems	The Parties recognise the need to establish, improve and enhance food security information systems, including national early warning systems, as well as, vulnerability assessment and monitoring systems, and implement capacity building actions, in conjunction with and through existing international and regional mechanisms.
-//-	-//-	Article 67	AGRICULTURE - Technology	The Parties recognise the importance of modern and sustainable agricultural technologies and agree to develop and promote the use of modern agricultural technologies that include: (a) sustainable irrigation and fertigation technologies; (b) tissue culture and micro propagation; (c) improved seed; (d) artificial insemination; (e) integrated pest management; (f) product packaging; (g) post-harvest handling; (h) accredited laboratories; (i) biotechnologies; (j) risk assessment and management.
-//-	-//-	Article 71	AGRICULTURE - Net Food Importing Countries	<p>1. The Parties recognise the importance of addressing the concerns of net food importing EAC Partner States. The objective of this Article therefore is to assist countries that are net food importers to develop programmes to ensure food security.</p> <p>2. The Parties agree to: (a) address constraints for food production, storage and distribution in EAC region (b) source food aid from within the EAC Partner States and other African Regional Economic Communities (c) improve coordination of food aid</p> <p>3. The Parties agree to maintain an adequate level of food aid, taking into account the interests of food aid recipients and to ensure that the measures mentioned in paragraph 2 do not unintentionally impede the delivery of food aid provided to deal with emergency situations.</p> <p>4. The Parties shall ensure that food aid is provided in full conformity with the measures that aim at preventing commercial displacement, which include: (a) ensuring that all food aid transactions are need driven and in full grant form; (b) not tying them directly or indirectly to commercial exports of agricultural products or of other goods and services.</p>

-//-	-//-	Article 72	AGRICULTURE - Importance of certain sectors	<p>1. The Parties recognise that: (a) provision of adequate access to food, clean and safe drinking water, health facilities, educational opportunities, housing, community participation and social integration is important for livelihood security of rural populations; (b) agricultural infrastructure development including production, processing, marketing and distribution plays crucial role in EAC Partner States' social-economic rural development and regional integration; (c) technical support services such as agricultural research, extension and advisory services training are important in increasing agricultural productivity; (d) facilitating agricultural financing is an important measure for transforming the agricultural sector in the EAC Partner States. Financing is required for agricultural technology development, agricultural credit and insurance, infrastructure development and markets as well as farmers' training; and (e) sustainable rural development is important to improve standards of living of the rural population of EAC Partner States.</p> <p>2. The Parties agree to cooperate in livelihood security, agricultural infrastructure, technical support services, agricultural financing services and rural development as provided for in Title II of Part V.</p>
-//-	-//-	Article 74	AGRICULTURE - Geographical indications	<p>1. The Parties recognise the importance of geographical indications for sustainable agriculture and rural development.</p> <p>2. The Parties agree to cooperate in the identification, recognition and registration of products that could benefit from protection as geographical indications and any other action aimed at achieving protection for identified products.</p>
Haiti	Economic Partnership Agreement between the CARIFORUM States, of the one part, and the European Community and its Member States, of the other part	Article 37	Agriculture and fisheries - Objectives	<p>1. The Parties agree that the fundamental objective of this Agreement is the sustainable development and the eradication of poverty in CARIFORUM States, and the smooth and gradual integration of these economies into the global economy. In the agricultural and fisheries sectors, this Agreement should contribute to increasing the competitiveness of production, processing and trade in agricultural and fishery products in both traditional and non-traditional sectors, between the Parties, consistent with the sustainable management of natural resources.</p> <p>4. The Parties recognise that ensuring food security and enhancing</p>

				livelihoods of rural and fishing communities are critical elements of the eradication of poverty, and the pursuit of sustainable development. They consequently recognise the need to avoid major disruption of markets for agricultural, food and fish products in CARIFORUM States.
New Zealand	Free Trade Agreement between the European Union and New Zealand	Article 7.4	SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS - Cooperation to improve the sustainability of food systems	4. The Parties shall cooperate on topics such as: (a) food production methods and practices which aim to improve sustainability, including organic farming and regenerative agriculture, amongst others; (b) the efficient use of natural resources and agricultural inputs, including reducing the use and risk of chemical pesticides and fertilisers, where appropriate; (c) the environmental and climate impacts of food production, including on agricultural greenhouse gas emissions, carbon sinks and biodiversity loss.

Appendix III: Case studies’ responses to questionnaires for the relevance of SDGs with policies as implemented locally

a. Organic farming certification

GOALS AND TARGETS (FROM THE 2030 AGENDA FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT)		6 ANALYSIS OF COCOA AND CHOCOLATE PURCHASING PRACTICES THAT COULD UNDERMINE LIVING INCOMES FOR COCOA FARMERS	1 Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Uganda and Tanzania	4 Priority intervention requirements to enhance the capacity of Sub Saharan African (SSA) countries to improve the volume and quality of agri-food exports			
				Cassava in Tanzania	Banana in Uganda	Goat Farming in Ethiopia	Cocoa in Ghana
GOAL 1. END POVERTY IN ALL ITS FORMS EVERYWHERE	1.1 By 2030, eradicate extreme poverty for all people everywhere, currently measured as people living on less than \$1.25 a day	3	1 0	1	3	1	3
	1.2 By 2030, reduce at least by half the proportion of men, women and children of all ages living in poverty in all its dimensions according to national definitions	3	1 0	1	3	1	3

GOAL 2. END HUNGER, ACHIEVE FOOD SECURITY AND IMPROVED NUTRITION AND PROMOTE SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE

2.1 By 2030, end hunger and ensure access by all people, in particular the poor and people in vulnerable situations, including infants, to safe, nutritious and sufficient food all year round	3	0	0	1	3	1	0
2.3 By 2030, double the agricultural productivity and incomes of small-scale food producers, in particular women, indigenous peoples, family farmers, pastoralists and fishers, including through secure and equal access to land, other productive resources and inputs, knowledge, financial services, markets and opportunities for value addition and non-farm employment	3	1	0	3	3	3	2
2.4 By 2030, ensure sustainable food production systems and implement resilient agricultural practices that increase productivity and production, that help maintain ecosystems, that strengthen capacity for adaptation to climate change, extreme weather, drought, flooding and other disasters and that progressively improve land and soil quality	2	1	0	3	3	3	2
2.5 By 2020, maintain the genetic diversity of seeds, cultivated plants and farmed and domesticated animals and their related wild species, including through soundly managed and diversified seed and plant banks at the national, regional and international levels, and promote access to and fair and	-1	2	0	3	3	3	2

	equitable sharing of benefits arising from the utilization of genetic resources and associated traditional knowledge, as internationally agreed							
	2.b Correct and prevent trade restrictions and distortions in world agricultural markets, including through the parallel elimination of all forms of agricultural export subsidies and all export measures with equivalent effect, in accordance with the mandate of the Doha Development Round	1	1	0	3	3	1	0
	2.c Adopt measures to ensure the proper functioning of food commodity markets and their derivatives and facilitate timely access to market information, including on food reserves, in order to help limit extreme food price volatility	0	1	0	3	3	1	3
GOAL 6. ENSURE AVAILABILITY AND SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF WATER AND SANITATION FOR ALL	6.6 By 2020, protect and restore water-related ecosystems, including mountains, forests, wetlands, rivers, aquifers and lakes	0	0	0	3	3	3	3
GOAL 8. PROMOTE SUSTAINED, INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH, FULL AND PRODUCTIVE EMPLOYMENT AND DECENT WORK FOR ALL	8.1 Sustain per capita economic growth in accordance with national circumstances and, in particular, at least 7 per cent gross domestic product growth per annum in the least developed countries	3	1	0	1	3	2	3
	8.2 Achieve higher levels of economic productivity through diversification, technological upgrading and innovation, including	1	1	1	3	3	2	3

	through a focus on high-value added and labour-intensive sectors							
	8.8 Protect labour rights and promote safe and secure working environments for all workers, including migrant workers, in particular women migrants, and those in precarious employment	1	1	0	3	3	2	3
GOAL 9. BUILD RESILIENT INFRASTRUCTURE, PROMOTE INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIALIZATION AND FOSTER INNOVATION	9.4 By 2030, upgrade infrastructure and retrofit industries to make them sustainable, with increased resource-use efficiency and greater adoption of clean and environmentally sound technologies and industrial processes, with all countries taking action in accordance with their respective capabilities	0	1	0	3	3	3	3
	9.b Support domestic technology development, research and innovation in developing countries, including by ensuring a conducive policy environment for, inter alia, industrial diversification and value addition to commodities	0	1	0	3	3	2	3
GOAL 10. REDUCE INEQUALITY WITHIN AND AMONG COUNTRIES	10.1 By 2030, progressively achieve and sustain income growth of the bottom 40 per cent of the population at a rate higher than the national average	3	1	0	3	3	2	3
	10.2 By 2030, empower and promote the social, economic and political inclusion of all, irrespective of age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or other status	2	1	0	3	3	2	3

GOAL 12. ENSURE SUSTAINABLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION PATTERNS	10.3 Ensure equal opportunity and reduce inequalities of outcome, including by eliminating discriminatory laws, policies and practices and promoting appropriate legislation, policies and action in this regard	1	1	0	3	3	2	3
	10.6 Ensure enhanced representation and voice for developing countries in decision-making in global international economic and financial institutions in order to deliver more effective, credible, accountable and legitimate institutions	3	1	0	3	3	3	3
	12.1 Implement the 10-Year Framework of Programmes on Sustainable Consumption and Production Patterns, all countries taking action, with developed countries taking the lead, taking into account the development and capabilities of developing countries	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
	12.2 By 2030, achieve the sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources	1	1	1	3	3	3	3
	12.4 By 2020, achieve the environmentally sound management of chemicals and all wastes throughout their life cycle, in accordance with agreed international frameworks, and significantly reduce their release to air, water and soil in order to minimize their adverse impacts on human health and the environment	1	1	2	1	1	1	1

	12.5 By 2030, substantially reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
	12.a Support developing countries to strengthen their scientific and technological capacity to move towards more sustainable patterns of consumption and production	0		0	-3	-3	-3	-3
GOAL 13. TAKE URGENT ACTION TO COMBAT CLIMATE CHANGE AND ITS IMPACTS	13.2 Integrate climate change measures into national policies, strategies and planning			0	3	3	3	3
GOAL 14. CONSERVE AND SUSTAINABLY USE THE OCEANS, SEAS AND MARINE RESOURCES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT	14.1 By 2025, prevent and significantly reduce marine pollution of all kinds, in particular from land-based activities, including marine debris and nutrient pollution	0	1	0	3	3	3	3
GOAL 15. PROTECT, RESTORE AND PROMOTE SUSTAINABLE USE OF TERRESTRIAL ECOSYSTEMS, SUSTAINABLY MANAGE FORESTS, COMBAT DESERTIFICATION, AND HALT AND REVERSE LAND DEGRADATION AND HALT BIODIVERSITY LOSS	15.1 By 2020, ensure the conservation, restoration and sustainable use of terrestrial and inland freshwater ecosystems and their services, in particular forests, wetlands, mountains and drylands, in line with obligations under international agreements	0	1	0	1	1	3	2
	15.3 By 2030, combat desertification, restore degraded land and soil, including land affected by desertification, drought and floods, and strive to achieve a land degradation-neutral world	0	1	0	1	1	3	2
	15.4 By 2030, ensure the conservation of mountain ecosystems, including their biodiversity, in order to enhance	0	1	0	1	1	3	2

	their capacity to provide benefits that are essential for sustainable development								
	15.5 Take urgent and significant action to reduce the degradation of natural habitats, halt the loss of biodiversity and, by 2020, protect and prevent the extinction of threatened species	1	1	0	1	1	3	2	

b. Food Safety Regulations

		1 Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Uganda and Tanzania		4 Priority intervention requirements to enhance the capacity of Sub Saharan African (SSA) countries to improve the volume and quality of agri-food exports			
				Cassava in Tanzania	Banana in Uganda	Goat Farming in Ethiopia	Cocoa in Ghana
Goal 1. End poverty in all its forms everywhere	1.1 By 2030, eradicate extreme poverty for all people everywhere, currently measured as people living on less than \$1.25 a day	-1	0	2	3	2	3
	1.2 By 2030, reduce at least by half the proportion of men, women and children of all ages living in poverty in all its dimensions according to national definitions	1	0	2	3	2	3
Goal 2. End hunger, achieve food security and improved	2.1 By 2030, end hunger and ensure access by all people, in particular the poor and people in vulnerable situations, including infants, to safe, nutritious and sufficient food all year round	1	0	3	3	2	3

nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture	2.3 By 2030, double the agricultural productivity and incomes of small-scale food producers, in particular women, indigenous peoples, family farmers, pastoralists and fishers, including through secure and equal access to land, other productive resources and inputs, knowledge, financial services, markets and opportunities for value addition and non-farm employment	1	0	3	3	3	3
	2.4 By 2030, ensure sustainable food production systems and implement resilient agricultural practices that increase productivity and production, that help maintain ecosystems, that strengthen capacity for adaptation to climate change, extreme weather, drought, flooding and other disasters and that progressively improve land and soil quality	2	0	3	3	3	3
	2.b Correct and prevent trade restrictions and distortions in world agricultural markets, including through the parallel elimination of all forms of agricultural export subsidies and all export measures with equivalent effect, in accordance with the mandate of the Doha Development Round	1	0	2	3	3	2
	2.c Adopt measures to ensure the proper functioning of food commodity markets and their derivatives and facilitate timely access to market information, including on food reserves, in order to help limit extreme food price volatility	1	0	2	3	3	3
Goal 3. Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages	3.9 By 2030, substantially reduce the number of deaths and illnesses from hazardous chemicals and air, water and soil pollution and contamination		2	3	2	1	2
Goal 8. Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable	8.1 Sustain per capita economic growth in accordance with national circumstances and, in particular, at least 7 per cent gross domestic product growth per annum in the least developed countries	2	0	2	3	2	3

economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all	8.2 Achieve higher levels of economic productivity through diversification, technological upgrading and innovation, including through a focus on high-value added and labour-intensive sectors	1	-1	2	3	2	3
Goal 9. Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation	9.4 By 2030, upgrade infrastructure and retrofit industries to make them sustainable, with increased resource-use efficiency and greater adoption of clean and environmentally sound technologies and industrial processes, with all countries taking action in accordance with their respective capabilities	-1	0	3	3	2	3
	9.b Support domestic technology development, research and innovation in developing countries, including by ensuring a conducive policy environment for, inter alia, industrial diversification and value addition to commodities	1	0	3	3	2	3
	10.1 By 2030, progressively achieve and sustain income growth of the bottom 40 percent of the population at a rate higher than the national average	1	0	2	3	2	3
	10.2 By 2030, empower and promote the social, economic and political inclusion of all, irrespective of age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or other status	1	0	2	3	2	3
Goal 10. Reduce inequality within and among countries	10.3 Ensure equal opportunity and reduce inequalities of outcome, including by eliminating discriminatory laws, policies and practices and promoting appropriate legislation, policies and action in this regard	1	0	2	3	2	3
	10.4 Adopt policies, especially fiscal, wage and social protection policies, and progressively achieve greater equality	1	0	2	2	2	3
	10.6 Ensure enhanced representation and voice for developing countries in decision-making in global international economic and financial institutions in order to deliver more effective, credible, accountable and legitimate institutions	1	0	1	2	2	3
Goal 12. Ensure	12.1 Implement the 10-Year Framework of Programmes	1	0	1	1	2	2

sustainable consumption and production patterns	on Sustainable Consumption and Production Patterns, all countries taking action, with developed countries taking the lead, taking into account the development and capabilities of developing countries						
	12.2 By 2030, achieve the sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources	1	1	3	3	2	3
	12.4 By 2020, achieve the environmentally sound management of chemicals and all wastes throughout their life cycle, in accordance with agreed international frameworks, and significantly reduce their release to air, water and soil in order to minimize their adverse impacts on human health and the environment	1	3	3	3	2	3
	12.a Support developing countries to strengthen their scientific and technological capacity to move towards more sustainable patterns of consumption and production	1	0	3	3	2	3